

**The Challenge in the Use of Economic Evaluation
for Health Care Decision Making in Local Level:
A Systematic Review**

By Nuke Hatta

Submitted: September 2017

*"This dissertation is submitted in part fulfilment of the M.Sc. in Health and Public Service
Management"*

*"I declare that this dissertation is the result of my
own independent investigation and that all sources are
duly acknowledged in the bibliography"*

29 September 2017,

Nuke Hatta, MD

Acknowledgement

First and foremost, I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisor who is also acting as the course leader of MSc. Health and Public Service Management, Mr. Colin Morgan, MSc. Also to my other lecturers: Gerwyn Henderson. MA., Prof. Catherine Farrell, and Dr. Jennifer Law. My gratitude goes to my classmates whom I could not mention their name one by one.

To my family back home, my son especially, Abrar Birbala Amadeus – my sole inspiration toward achieving my dream; I couldn't express enough how lucky I am to have your supports and prayers. To my best friends at home, 'The Sisters' club, to my Indonesian Chevening friends, to my gang 'USW Chevening' pals, and the rest of my friends here in UK who always there for me through thick and thin. To my newest friends Zoe and Mark, thank you for believing me and comfort me during my tough days. My special thanks to my best friends during my study here in USW: Otgo, June, Ruva, Anggie; best comforters – loyalists and true friends.

Last but not least, to CHEVENING Scholarships, the UK government's global scholarship programme, funded by the Foreign and Commonwealth Office (FCO) and partner organisations; to which I was given the opportunity to study this master degree in the first place. Thank you so much.

Abstract

Background: Health economic evaluation gained its importance in the last couple of decades to deal with the scarce resource allocation. The establishment of UK NICE guidelines further emphasized the need for cost-effectiveness consideration during decision-making process. However, several authors have reported that the impact of health economics studies in local health care decision-making probably limited due to several factors. The purpose of this study is to investigate the current use of health economic evaluation among local health care decision makers and evaluate the existing barriers that might impede the extend use of the economic studies for priority-settings agenda.

Methods: The systematic review using qualitative approach is employed for this purpose. Four databases were scrutinized for the literatures discussing the topic under observation. Three types of literatures included in this study namely: primary research papers, systematic review type of papers and non-research papers. All then subjected for further evaluation and critically appraised.

Results: In total 14 literatures is included in this systematic review consist of: 7 primary qualitative researches, 2 systematic reviews, and 4 non-research papers written by health economists. Each of the papers had investigate the extend use of health economic evaluations in decision-making and identified the barriers according to the participants views and proposed some solutions to tackle those impediments. This study then compiled, analysed and synthesised all the findings and came up with final argumentations for future research consideration.

Conclusions: There was a conclusive evidence how the use of health economic evaluation for priority-setting among local health care decision makers somewhat lacking. From several barriers that had been identified suggesting that health economists need to further understand the local needs and provide more contextual answers for the local problems. Further research, especially in investigating the micro-level decision making constraints to employ the health economic evaluations results in the practices, is necessarily required.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER I BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY	1
1.1 Research Questions	6
1.2 Aims & Objectives.....	6
CHAPTER II THE LITERATURE BACKGROUND IN HEALTH ECONOMICS	8
2.1 Health Economics	8
Health Economics and Scarcity	8
Health Economics and Equity	8
2.2 Health Economic Evaluation	11
What is Health Economic Evaluation?.....	11
Why Economic Evaluation in Health Care?.....	11
The Anthithetical Approaches to the Use of Health Economic Evaluation in Decision Making.....	14
Basic Types of Health Economic Evaluation.....	21
The Use of Decision Analytic Modelling in Health Economic Evaluations.....	30
CHAPTER III RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND STUDY DESIGN	32
Study Design.....	32
Materials and Methods	34
Selection Criteria	34
Search Strategy.....	35
Data Extraction	37
Data Appraisal.....	38
Data Synthesis.....	38
CHAPTER IV RESULTS.....	40
Databases search finding.....	40
Characteristics of the findings	41
Primary Research Papers.....	42
Systematic Review Papers.....	45
Non-research Papers	46
Critical Appraisal.....	46
Primary Research Paper	46
Systematic Reviews.....	48
The Use of Economic Evaluation in Local Health Care Decision Making	48
The Barriers to Utilize the Health Economic Evaluation into decision making process.....	49
The Solutions as revealed in the Studies	53
CHAPTER V DISCUSSION	55
The Actual Use of Economic Evaluations in Local Health Care Decision Making	57

The barriers and possible solutions to increase the uptake of the health economic evaluations into decision making process.....	58
Extrinsic Barriers and Facilitators	58
Intrinsic Barriers	62
CHAPTER VI CONCLUSION	67
CHAPTER VII RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE WORK.....	69
REFERENCES.....	70
APPENDICES	a

LIST OF TABLES:

TABLE 1. INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA..... 35
TABLE 2. KEYWORDS USED AND BOOLEAN OPERATOR 37
TABLE 3. SUMMARY OF THE TYPE OF LITERATURES.....41
TABLE 4. SUMMARY GEOGRAPHY AND HEALTH CARE SYSTEM (PRIMARY RESEARCH PAPERS) . 43
TABLE 5. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMARY RESEARCH PAPERS44
TABLE 6. SUMMARY OF THE CHARACTERISTIC OF SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS 45
TABLE 7. SUMMARY OF NON-RESEARCH PAPERS46
TABLE 8. CASP QUALITATIVE RESEARCH CHECKLIST (APPENDIX I)47
TABLE 9. CASP CRITICAL CHECKLISTS FOR SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS (APPENDIX II)48

LIST OF FIGURES:

FIGURE 1. HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION: WEIGHING COST VERSUS BENEFIT11
FIGURE 2. CALCULATING ICER..... 23
FIGURE 3. THE EXPONENTIAL GROWTH OF CUA 26
FIGURE 4. SIMPLE CALCULATION OF QALYS (TAKEN FROM TERNOPIL STATE MEDICAL
UNIVERSITY, NO DATE) 26
FIGURE 5. DECISION ANALYTIC MODELLING 31
FIGURE 6. FLOW DIAGRAM OF SEARCH RESULTS AND DATA EXTRACTION41

APPENDICES:

Appendix I. CASP Checklist Qualitative Research a
Appendix II. CASP Checklist Qualitative Systematic Review f

CHAPTER I

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The idea of health or health care economics is to assess the usage of health technologies and activities using a perspective of an economist. Health technology, by definition, is not limited to medical device or technology alone, but it is also covering all aspects from medical interventions, surgical techniques, screening procedures to public health programmes and health services (Lessard et al., 2009). With that said, a health economics or a health care economics is being utilized to define how efficient the resource allocation to a certain health care technology under a scarcity condition (Drummond, 1993a; Folland et al., 2004; Kobelt, 2013; Scott et al., 2001). As Goeree and Diaby (2013) explained that in health care market, a demand will always outstrip a supply. The inquiry for a better health service, better medication, better improvement in surgical technique, etc, is continuously growing, surpassing the capacity and capability from the healthcare provider to provide it. Therefore, it is pivotal to use health economic analysis to assure that the implementation of the new health technology achieved its best value whilst also cost-effective.

Further to its development, health economic evaluation has been used as a guidance for decision makers in defining the choice of deploying resources to certain health product or service in relative to its alternatives. The economist perspective in seeing the dilemma from the point of a view of scarce resources (namely funding, time, workforces, facilities, knowledge, etc), is intended to derive with a rational efficiency judgement for a decision maker to prioritize to (Evans and Hurley, 1995). Hence, health economic assessment become valuable input for decision maker to decide which program or services could be valued as the best possible choice from multiple options available in term of its cost-effectiveness and efficiency (Briggs et al., 2006; Drummond et al., 2005). This choice pursued by the decision makers, which derived upon the question on which program should get the funding or should receive more priority, ought

to be constructed carefully so that the allocation of constraint resources could accomplish its best 'value for money' (Drummond, 1993b). Drummond et al. (2005, p. 9) wrote that "*the basic tasks of any economic evaluation are to identify, measure, value, and compare the costs and consequences of the alternatives being considered*". Correspondingly, it could be summarised that the main function of the economic evaluation in health care is to act as the provider of information acquired from rigorous analytical course to assist the health care decision maker in selecting the cutting-edge health technologies, in term of its cost-effectiveness and efficiency; as well as to improve the current health care practices.

Nevertheless, translating the health economic evaluation results to a readily used guidance for a decision maker, is not an easy task. Drummond et al. (2005) wrote that despite its importance, health economic evaluation may not be useful for making a definitive decision unless it already preceded by a study concerning efficacy, effectiveness/usefulness and availability. A health economic evaluation, as they continued, could only solves the problem or sees the perspective of the object under observation, from one angle or one dimension. Similarly, Brousselle and Lessard (2011) pointed out that several authors have shown that the health economic evaluation criterion from several studies had proven to be inadequate. They explained that within those researches, some of the values that have been used to analyse efficiency and priority setting could not give a satisfying result due to its nature to neglect some of the impeding factors that could influence the whole setting. In example, they added, that the study conducted by Tengs et al. (1996) using cost-utility analysis, had failed to provide reasonable guidance for US decision maker in term of choosing the health care service priority to receive the Medicaid coverage. In this study, an odd result appeared that a life-saving intervention was being considered less efficient compare to minor condition like treatment for headache, hence suggested to receive less funding whilst the fact that a life-saving intervention is far more critical situation in real-life setting compare to headache. Likewise, McGregor (2003) cited that the use of QALYs in determining the cost-effectiveness in the use of sildenafil, a

medication to treat an erectile dysfunction, in the study conducted by Smith and Roberts (2000) is doubly to be significant. He argued that despite the result stated that consuming sildenafil five times monthly would costing less per QALYs in comparison to renal dialysis, hypercholesterolemia medication and coronary artery bypass grafting, but in reality, those ailments mentioned later were the one who could alter somebody's health status more significantly. Furthermore, to devise a rational decision making in health care continued become a challenge for any policy maker, judging from the fact that health itself is composed of multi-facets with multiple stake-holders involved.

Nonetheless, Goeree and Diaby (2013) convinced that an economic evaluation has been widely accepted as an effective tool to assist decision making process both in macro and meso level, especially under uncertainty circumstances. A steady rise of health care expenditure in contrast with Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has forced, even some developed countries, including UK, to tighten their spending with austerity, hence the growing need for health care decision maker to constitute an economic based evaluation for the health care provision, in recent days (Morris et al., 2007; Sculpher et al., 2006). Furthermore, according to Morris et al. (2007, p. 345-351) the increasing use of economic evaluation in decision making is driven by these four motives:

1. *"To maximise the benefits from health care spending."*
2. *"To overcome regional variations in access."*
3. *"To contain costs and manage demand."*
4. *"To provide bargaining power with suppliers of health care products."*

Subsequently, Hjelmgren et al. (2001) wrote that due to the urgent needs to create efficiency in health care, government in several countries had pushed forward the establishment of a guideline for health economic evaluation. These guidelines have been provided to assist the decision maker in deciding the input price and the reimbursement strategy, especially for

pharmaceutical industry. In Wales and England, National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) was being established in 1999. The main purpose is to provide a national guidance for NHS to adopt new health technology or intervention based on the study of cost-effectiveness, making sure that the equity of health services would be achieved while also considering the budget constraint. This guidance provided by NICE had been used to help decision maker in the area of public health to assess for example, the new program related to promotion and prevention. Therefore, such guidance intended to solve some of the problems faced not only by NHS in UK but also to act as decision tool for local authorities and public sectors in general. Likewise, the challenge faced by European countries regarding the increase in pharmaceutical expenditure, has forced the government several countries like Germany, Netherland, Sweden, Norway, and Denmark to establish a formal referencing guideline to set a national price for pharmaceutical products. Prior to that establishment, Australia (Commonwealth Department of Health) and Canada (Ministry of Health) in 1992 and 1994, respectively, had excelled others with their formulation of guidelines to use economic evaluation in public health arena (Briggs et al., 2006; Hutton, 2012; Rutten, 1996).

However, despite such effort to adopt the result of health economic evaluation studies as an effective decision tool and also as part of the attempt to produce an evidence-based policy making (Barrett, 2011; McCaughey and Bruning, 2010), it is argued if such studies had already accomplished its designated goal to assist the decision makers in creating more efficient and cost-effective health care provision (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011; Drummond et al., 1993; Lessard et al., 2009; Rutten, 1996; Sculpher et al, 2006). In England and Wales, for instance, despite the existence of NICE guidance to support the local decision makers in providing cost-effective treatments or programs, the adoption and the implementation of such guidelines lingered in grey area (Sheldon et al., 2004). Likewise, recent study conducted by Franken et al. (2016) scrutinizing the implementation of health economic evaluation from 4 countries (UK, Netherlands, Sweden, and Germany) concluded that there were plausible evidences that the

impact of the health economics studies on those countries were limited and ethical problem might be one of the possible element for it. Country like Germany, for instance, has struggled to cope with its historical background with NAZI regime, that most likely caused current rejection over the notion of priority setting based on cost-effectiveness. As it is clearly stated in The German Social Code Book V *“that anyone who needs a treatment is entitled to receive it”* (Franken et al., 2016, pp. 952) and as it evidenced by the case of a Duchenne muscular dystrophy patient¹ who, in 2005, won the Germany High Court against the insurance scheme (SHI – the Germany Statutory Health Insurance), that at first refused to fund the avant-garde treatment for this patient; because the Germany High Court found that the patient needs were pivotal to take into account.

Moreover, Drummond et al. (2005) stated the extend of the readers comprehensible to the results of the health economic studies, to be able to apply it in their own setting, is still not clear. Buchanan and Wordsworth (2015), for example, concluded that the different theoretical approaches for health economic evaluation had led to the confusion in the decision maker part, therefore could impede the adoption process of the results. Whilst, Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000) on their survey covering nine European countries including UK (Finland, Spain, Austria, Germany, Norway, Portugal, France and Netherlands), found that despite the growing belief that economic evaluation is crucial as the guidance for program prioritizing, only small amount of decision makers is utilizing it in real setting. Respectively, Eddama and Coast (2009) added that the application of economic evaluation studies among primary health care provider in UK was very limited. Similarly, Goeree and Diaby (2013) believed that the role of health economic evaluation in micro level still dubious by quoting Cunningham (2001) who studied the relevancy and ethical issues of conducting health economic appraisal among dentists. Drummond (2004) in his review paper pointed out several evidences how the

¹ it is the type of an early onset of muscular dystrophy disease, mostly as early as the first 3 years of life, and with short life expectancy, mostly patient died before the age of 10 (<https://www.mda.org/disease/duchenne-muscular-dystrophy>).

perspective of decision makers about the usefulness and the practicality aspect of the health economic analysis studies were varied, thus for them who were doubtful, would hesitate in employing it in their settings. However, Drummond (2004) believed any attempt to identify those impending factors would bring significant impacts in the future and might improve the adoption of the health economic evaluation studies in the decision-making process.

1.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Given the understanding that adopting health economic evaluation to devise a rational decision making is pivotal, but with the growing concern that the usage of such findings in real health care setting might be limited, therefore this paper would like to explore the 'why' on this issue by addressing several queries:

1. How is the use of economic evaluations among health care decision makers in meso and micro level (local level)?
2. What are the current perceived impediments in the application of the health economic evaluation results for decision making in local level?
3. What are the solutions provided so far to tackle those obstacles?
4. What can be recommended for future development on the study of the use of economic evaluation in health care decision making?

1.2 AIMS & OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to investigate the use and the barriers that impede the use of health economic evaluations for health care decision-making at the local level.

Further to achieve the study's aim, several objectives are set as follows:

1. to conduct a systematic review using the qualitative approach.

2. to set a systematic databases search strategy using the targeted keywords matched the topic's aim.
3. to collect previous literatures discussing the use and the barriers of health economics studies for decision-making purposes among local decision makers.
4. To analyse and synthesise the finding to answer the current research's questions.

CHAPTER II

THE LITERATURE BACKGROUND IN HEALTH ECONOMICS

2.1 HEALTH ECONOMICS

HEALTH ECONOMICS AND SCARCITY

Because we live in the world in which scarcity in resources is inevitable, consequently any attempt to produce goods would come under circumstances where a choice should be taken or an option must be made.

However, to make sure that the choices made are impeccable, it should excogitate the aspect of the expected benefit and the opportunity cost.² In another word, the scarce resources need to be allocated efficiently to make sure it obtains its maximum value. Since a health care provision is not exempted from such predicament, hence a health economic plays an important role in term of helping a decision maker to make the appropriate choice in health care, among alternatives that existed. The objective of measuring health in economic point a view is to maximize the benefit gained and to minimize the opportunity cost that occurred, thus ensuring efficiency (Morris et al., 2007; Douglas and Normand, 2005).

HEALTH ECONOMICS AND EQUITY

Since the resource is scarce, human then needs to consider a proper way to distribute the resource so much so that everyone feels satisfied. The foundation of Welfare Economics

² Most common and simple description of Opportunity Cost as taken from www.economicshelp.org is “*the next best alternative foregone*”. An interesting outlook on this notion is the exploration in the term “true cost” by Henderson (2008) when he took an example in the postgraduate student tuition fee and government scholarship scheme to half funded the study. On paper, as if like the government had funded the study more than 65% out of total, but in reality, the ‘hidden cost’ which is the best foregone alternative, in the way that the student must deserted their valuable time to work thus earn money, might be way higher. Hence, the actual percentage of the cost covered by the government in the scholarship scheme was smaller than it seemed. With a similar analogy but with a different approach is explained when the cost of living as a student was being measured. Although on paper the student living cost might be added to the extrapolation, but it did not affect the cost in actual term, because regardless the student in the study mode or not, he/she might need to pay for the living cost nonetheless.

tenet is one that set the rule of thumbs for such complexity. In health care, it is always being a dilemma for decision makers to decide on how or what way to fairly distribute the constraint health resources (the difference in approaches had made the health economist split into two major tenets called welfarist and extra-welfarist). The equity, of course, should be distinguished from the term equality, although the aspect of inequalities of the health distribution which prominent in the society, was the main provocation for health economists to derive with the formulation for economic assessment in health to reach the state of equity. However, there is no consensus among experts on which value judgment should be used to define what is equity in health care, so much so that it is difficult to answer the question on 'how to achieve it' (Mooney, 1992). The adversity in weighing the equity in health care is an ongoing 'unsolved' issue. The problem on how to weigh the equity in health, for example, could be seen in the case when the policy makers, in their act within the paternalistic realm, have to decide the allocative budget between a group of smokers and the non-smokers. The later batch, was perceived to be held responsible for their action, therefore any consequences arrived from such 'reckless' activity, such as coronary heart disease or lung cancer, should not be regarded 'equal' with the nonsmokers population of whom might suffer for the same ailments from others predisposing factors, during the calculation for resource allocation; although this had created ethical concern thus problematic (Tsuchiya and Williams, 2001). Mooney (1992) therefore explored the basis of "NEED" to be used in relation to the equal allocative resources for health care provision. Similarly, Sen (1979) with his critics to orthodox welfarism, argued that individual characteristic as defined by their 'capabilities' and 'functionings', should be taken into account when setting prioritization for resources allocation. These personal traits, as Sen argued, could be seen as the basis for different NEED hence moving away from simply measuring individual utilities in monetary term. However, it is debatable later on whether QALYs as the unit of health computation using Sen's as the philosophical background, could be seen as the equity measurement or just mere efficiency (Bobinac et al., 2012; Mitton and Donaldson, 2004; Soares,

2012; Wagstaff, 1991; Whitehead and Ali, 2010). For as Mooney (1992) said that what deemed to be efficient may not be equitable and vice versa.

Furthermore, to address the equity in society means to determine 'who deserves what' and who authorized to judge 'who deserves what'. This has brought enough confusion, let alone be able to encrypt another enigma surrounding the equity notion which is 'how to distribute' (Mooney, 1992, Brazier et al., 2007). In Sen's theory of '*physical-condition neglect*' and '*valuation neglect*' as explained by Mooney and Russell (2003, p. 208), people possessed the ability to adapt with his lacking or disability, thereof their expectation may be adjusted to certain level that, in term of health/happiness, what considered to be 'worse off' by alternate group within the same community may not be as truth as to compare with their 'realistic' feeling. Just say, if someone born blind since birth. This person may appreciate being able to perceive blurry images by receiving cutting edge treatment in ophthalmology, probably more than the appreciation detected from someone who suffered from visual impairment like myopia or hypermetropia in later life but born in normal sight. The slight alteration to this individual visual acuity brought a significant difference to their level of satisfaction, compared to someone with different baseline state. However, it is a question for debate, whether to allocate budget, thereof, prioritizing to this certain group, by all means, could be translated as an equity (Mooney and Russell, 2003). The different approaches in which cost, value and benefit could be measured, are remained unsettled among health economists. Nevertheless, the pursuit of equitable distribution of goods, including health care, is never at rest, and the health economic evaluation continues to grow within this paradigm to achieve its greater state for the welfare of society as a whole.

2.2 HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION

WHAT IS HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION?

By definition, a health economic evaluation means *“the comparative analysis of alternative courses of action in terms of both their cost and consequences”* (Drummond et al., 2005, p. 9). Morris et al. (2007, p. 209) explained health economic evaluation as *“a broad set of analytical approaches used to describe and compare the benefits and costs of competing uses of resources.”*

Figure 1. health economic evaluation: weighing cost versus benefit

WHY ECONOMIC EVALUATION IN HEALTH CARE?

As explained in the chapter background of this study, an economic evaluation has taken an important role in assessing health technologies, especially with current development where there is an increasing need to provide an evidence-based studies that answered some of the problems related to resources allocation (McCaughey and Bruning, 2010). In short, the objective of conducting health economic evaluations is to maximize the health gained in the population regardless the scarcity in resources (Drummond et al., 2005; Kobelt, 2013; McIntosh and Luengo-Fernandez, 2006; McPake et al., 2002, Mooney, 1992; Morris et al., 2007; Rice, 2003). Furthermore, the health economic evaluations could act as the systematic analysis to determine the best health care programs or service among the available alternatives to which pertinent to

the objectives that the decision maker wishes to achieve (Douglas and Normand, 2005; Drummond et al., 2005). In the example of this is when a decision maker in meso/micro level, namely a local government or public health practitioners or physicians, wishes to undertake an evaluation of a new program related to a treatment for the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. The economists then need to investigate the cost-effectiveness of the new medication to treat the disease and to compare it with its alternatives, such as preventive programs related to the progression of the ailment, just say like a smoking cessation. Not only that economic evaluation would assist the decision makers in identifying the alternatives, but the adoption of health economic evaluations would also give valuable insights in understanding the benefit that forgone (opportunity cost). In this case, a systematic analysis provided by health economic evaluations might result in the alteration of the preceding proposal, by showing that preventive program such as smoking cessation might be more cost-effective to achieve a desirable result (the overall number of patients 'expected' to suffer for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease would decrease with more efficient budget to spend), in comparison with the new drug's treatment. However, as the Drummond et al. (2005) also pointed out that since health care comprises of multi-facets, therefore there are various aspects to consider and an economic evaluation might not be able to give a comprehensive answer to everything, but it is at least able to minimize the risk of making an irrational decision in health care. Correspondingly, Heyland et al. (1999) wrote that the use of economic evaluations should never be the main and the only basis for making a clinical judgment or decision making in local health care setting, despite they admitted the importance.

Furthermore, it is indeed crucial to take the diverse standpoints into consideration during an economic analysis study, because it would help revealing broader perspective by overviewing the issue under observation from all the possible angles. With such contingency has been taken into account, it would allow the decision makers to justify their decision by making sure that all the alternatives viewpoints had been assessed accordingly, therefore the

best and the most desirable outcome is chosen (Drummond et al., 2005). Without addressing the multiple perspectives, the result of decision is unlikely attainable. Taken as an example, in the case when the decision makers have to figure out whether or not to conduct a screening for colon cancer. In a point of view of policy makers or clinicians, a screening for people age 50 or above might help to reduce the mortality rate up to 2.5%, thus seems to be a perfect option to choose from. However, if we valued patient perspective, considering the side effect of colonoscopy, this procedure might not be their best option, especially there were also existing study that revealed the detrimental effects of colonoscopy like perforation, excessive bleeding and adverse cardiovascular event, which reached higher percentage up to 2.8% (Barret, 2011). Such weighing between risks and benefits alongside with the opportunity costs using various perspectives (targeted population, patients, clinicians, policy makers, society in general) would be best administered using health economic analysis, although this statement *per se* is debatable.

Accordingly, an economic evaluation would also deal with the uncertainty arise in the order of magnitude, by measuring the value of the benefits rather than just assessing the cost of the object under study. This is pivotal to comprehend because in determining the real cost of a program, it is not so much about calculating the expenditure in term of money or the actual cost of goods, but it is more about calculating the benefits that forgone or the opportunity cost (Drummond et al., 2005; Graves et al., 2005). In fact, as it is demonstrated by the story of ‘the sixth stool guaiac’, an experiment conducted by Neuhauser and Lewicki in 1975, a marginal cost measurement in economic analysis is also imperative to get the real value of the object under observation, which in that case mentioned, was the cost for the sixth screening test for colorectal cancer³ (Brown and Burrows, 1990; Money and Drummond, 1982; Walker et al., 1991).

³ A six sequential chromographic screening tests for colon cancer was conducted in US. The result was unexpected. The marginal cost, which is the extra cost per new case detected – the sixth screening test, was reaching the inexplicable number which was up to 47 million USD. This was an increase of approximately 20,000 times compare to the average cost.

THE ANTHITHETICAL APPROACHES TO THE USE OF HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION IN DECISION MAKING

Commonly, the economist will use two distinguished approaches in doing the health economic analysis, namely *the welfarist* and *the extra-welfarist*. These divisions would influence the presentation of the results of the health economic analysis based on which perspective in determining which valuable taken into account. Consequently, it would alter the value judgment of the decision makers (Hutton, 2012). Buchanan and Wordsworth (2015) in their study found that the choice of approach for economic evaluations in health care would affect significantly on the behavior of the decision makers whether or not to adopt such study in their setting. The conflicting results which led to later confusion (in term of choosing the most appropriate health technology or intervention), were common among decision makers, especially under situation when there was evidence of at least 22% of health economics studies applying two different approaches (Buchanan and Wordsworth, 2015). We will, hitherto, discussed briefly both theories and the ongoing debate surrounding it.

THE WELFARIST APPROACH

The welfarist theory is described as “*the systemic analysis of the social desirability of any set of arrangements, for example, a state of the world or allocation of resources, solely in terms of the utility obtained by individuals*” (Morris et al., 2007). Thereof, when we spoke about the welfarist approach, it basically considering the welfare of collective individuals or the society in its whole. Thus, if there is an existence of two equal social states in term of their distribution of personal well-being, these two states would be considered comparable, despite the existence of differences in other respects (Gravel and Moyes, 2011). In another saying, welfarism considered the social welfare as the sum of utilities possessed by each of the individual within that particular group. Therefore, the aim of welfarism is to achieve the optimum societal welfare under the condition of limited budget distributed among the members of the society (Buchanan and Wordsworth, 2015). Accordingly, to attain such objective as described above, the social

judgment will be delivered on the basis of the framework of classical economist known as the 'Pareto Principle' (Brouwer et al., 2008; Morris et al., 2007). The fundamental idea using this approach were surrounded around the norm of Pareto Improvement. It explained as follow: because the individuals are regarded to be the best judged for their own welfare (state of well-being) therefore the Pareto Improvement was achieved when an individual can be made 'better off' with no one within the same societal group is made 'worse off' with such alteration (Coast et al., 2008; McPake et al., 2002).

However, accomplishing such standard in the real world is difficult, if not to say impossible (Brazier et al., 2007; Morris et al., 2007, Tsuchiya and Williams, 2001). Just say, if an individual gained its utility (better off) from the development of a public road that creates a good access to his office, the others may be worse off by suffering from pollution due to the incomplete combustion of the car engines (McPake et al., 2002). To address this inconclusiveness, *Kaldor* and *Hicks* came with the theory which later classified as the Potential Pareto improvement (Coast et al., 2008; Brazier et al., 2007). Within this basis of paradigm, if someone, who may be the gainer of the utility provided, is able to compensate the loser (the one who is worse off by the provided products), then eventually all can be a winner or better off or no one would actually worse off. Brazier et al. (2007) argued that despite adjusting the practical issue of the Pareto Improvement with the Potential Pareto Improvement may seems justice, however even in such scenario it is not yet addressing the equity in the distribution of goods. Nevertheless, since according to Pareto's framework, the augmentation of individual utilities (welfare) would directly translate as the increase in societal welfare, it faced difficulty in determining which utility gained by different person that altered the social welfare, let alone having a basis to compare it (Coast et al., 2008; McPake et al., 2002). Another restriction accessible within this framework, is the circumspection in valuing the health profiles from different group population, despite the ordinal rankings of the welfare gained, had been established (Brazier et al., 2007; McPake et al., 2002).

The translation of the Potential Pareto Improvement in an applied economic analysis is called Cost-Benefit Analysis or CBA. The application of this method of health economic evaluation quite common in the 1970s (Buchanan and Wordsworth, 2015, Hutton, 2012). We will further discuss CBA later on this paper.

THE EXTRA-WELFARIST APPROACH

As argumentation around welfarism continued, some economist came with the opponent theory to the former, which still rooted in the Pareto Principle. If the welfarism is more concern with the accumulative personal utilities to enhance, or the individual is being perceived as the utility maximiser thus the resources would be allocated in this preference (McPake et al., 2002; Morris et al., 2007; Seixas, 2017); the 'extra' welfarist was purposing an alternative approach which is to maximize the overall health status of the society (Culyer, 1989; Seixas, 2017). It is Amyrta Sen, a professor at Harvard University, who first advocated the debate to challenge the welfarist practitioners who were emphasizing on the individual utility, with his notions of "capabilities" and "functioning" (Sen, 1979). To Sen belief, assessing the social welfare through a mere an individual utility gained is ambiguous, since an individual perception of 'satisfaction' is being influenced by their embedded characteristic which explained by Sen as 'capabilities', which is "*the freedoms that an individual has to make choices*", and 'functionings', which is "*what an individual manages to be*" (Morris et al., 2007, p. 234). Hence, the necessity to conjoin the 'extra' information of characteristics of individual, because this would make an impact on their choice and perception of the 'well-being' (welfare), is the basic foundation for extra-welfarist approach (Brouwer et al., 2008; Coast et al., 2008; McPake et al, 2002; Morris et al., 2007, Richardson and McKie, 2004). The extra-welfarist in this sense did not try to neglect the individual utility, rather tried to define it based on the proposition that the perceived merits would be significantly different, thus capable in altering the individual act in pursuing their needs. This act, in which it influenced by their inert characteristics, may not always be *vis a vis*

with what is considered as 'the best thing' in the paternalistic viewpoint (Brouwer et al., 2008; Seixas, 2017). Taken as an example is the different degree of happiness which depends broadly on how an individual valuing their life, can be seen in the comparison between someone with a depression trait and someone who is a cancer survivor. Based on the equity context, allocating resources to increase the utility to these two-distinguished group would be unfair, if a person, due to his inherited trait, would not be able to appreciate it as much as the second one. Hence, the theory of Sen's individual characteristic is more favorable to resource allocation in decision-making, in a sense, it could also possible to tackle the shortcoming in welfarist approach to equity (although this proposition continued as a contentious issue).

Further, conceding that using welfarist approach, the individual welfare state could be assessed from the commodities (including services) that being utilized; the extra-welfarist, in the other hand, is taking the emphasize further into the non-utility state of individual (Culyer, 1989; Morris et al., 2007) like the degree of quality of life, happiness, the pain-free event etc; henceforth to the extra-welfarist adherents, this approach could transform the way public policy, especially the one concerning general health status, being measured. Moreover, the aspect of 'relationship' inter individuals also made its important ground within the extra-welfarist's mind; consequently, any economic evaluation should consider the unique quality that embedded in certain groups within a population (Culyer, 1989). This approach then adjusted to the health economic evaluation in term of valuing the benefit gained, using for instance, QALYs (quality-adjusted life-years)⁴ which commonly being measured in the form of cost-effectiveness analysis and cost-utility analysis (Buchanan and Wordsworth, 2015; McPake et al, 2002; Morris et al., 2007; Seixas, 2017). If economic evaluation using welfarist approach in a form of Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) received a considerably defiance from the health

⁴ The QALYs is the most common used standard to measure individual state of health in term of their quality of life. The economist translated the 'quality of life' comparable with the 'health state' which one perceived by measuring it with the extend of life one gained upon receiving 'manipulation'. With QALYs in hand, the health decision makers would be able to answer the question on which groups deserved the priority more in health resource allocation, thus explained its vast usage in health care society.

practitioners and public sectors, because its tendency toward valuing health in the monetary term which could be easily perceived unethical to most people and the 'willingness to pay' would be detrimental in term of discrimination toward the poor (Brazier et al., 2007, Tsuchiya and Williams, 2001), contrastingly Cost-effectiveness Analysis (CEA) and Cost-Utility Analysis (CUA), the extra-welfarist approach on economic evaluation, had gained its widely acceptance especially at the macro level (Buchanan and Wordsworth, 2015; Dolan and Edlin, 2002, Hutton, 2012), particularly with the establishment of NICE in UK, and similar bodies in Australia and Canada. In UK, as a matter of fact, the government had been explicitly mentioned the objective of their health policy written in the 1994 White Paper on NHS which closely correlated to the tenet of the extra-welfarist (as quoted by Brouwer et al. 2008, p. 16 quoting Van Doorslaer et al., 1993), saying "*The government (...) wants to ensure that in the future every man, woman, and child can rely on getting (...) the best medical and other facilities available; that their getting them **shall not depend on whether they can pay for them or any other factor irrelevant to real need***".

Nevertheless, it could be summarized that the difference between the extra-welfarist approach compare to welfarist constituted in several degrees: "*(i) it permits the use of outcome other than utility, (ii) it permits the use of sources of evaluation other than the affected individuals, (iii) it permits the weighting of outcomes (whether utility or other) according to principles that need not be preference-based and (iv) it permits interpersonal comparisons of well-being in a variety of dimensions, thus enabling moving beyond Paretian economics.*" (Brouwer et al., 2008, p. 14). And the extra-welfarist approach is the reaction toward what some economists perceived as the major flaws within the tenet of individual sovereignty using the classical Pareto Principles as purposed by the welfarism, in which they convinced that the welfarism might not be at best applied into health care sector settings. However, the debate between the welfarist and the extra-welfarist continued, and some criticism also directed to the extra-welfarist. The elaboration on this, subsequently.

IS EXTRA-WELFARISM STILL RELEVANT?

As it already mentioned, the extra-welfarist approach which emerged from the critic toward the orthodox tradition of welfarism, is not free from skeptic judgment. For example, Richardson and McKie (2005) argued that the extra-welfarist approach which fundamentally grounded to Sen's theory of 'capabilities' and 'functionings' were suffered from the difficulty to weigh things, whenever there is multiple possibilities to appraise the term 'valuable'. It also had been criticised for using solely health maximisation as the main basis for prioritizing health care budget. To this argumentation, other aspects outside health (the non-health utilities) may be directly or indirectly pertinent with health interventions. And the outcome (benefit) perceived could be expanded than mere just 'a health quality' measurement (Coast et al., 2008' Morris et al., 2007). The program helped to tackle the obesity problem, for instance, should not just be valued from the health perspective since it also affected the individual self-image and self-esteem, which in turn altered their productivity. If this aspect is being neglected, and the focus of attention of decision makers solely based on the QALYs, it may well result in the program being less funded compared to the alternatives, despite the resultant impact on the overall well-being (the individual 'welfare' state) somewhat higher. A similar example is taken from the study about teenage pregnancy and early childbearing conducted by Furstenberg (2016) which argued that the policy to restrict such event ought not to eliminate the value of other major impacts to the unfortunate teens, such as the increased opportunity for continuing to higher education and the jobs prospective.

Another 'harsh' exposition toward extra-welfarist tenet is directed against the imposing of the external judgment toward one state of well-being without giving an individual the chance of preferences. The paternalistic view of extra-welfarism has been considered unjust to the equity goals. If the less fortunate preferences being neglected or the 'capacity to manage the desire' is discounted, then the state of equity in health hardly achievable (at least in context).

This could be seen as a problem in the distribution of preferences among subgroups within population, as everyone or collected individuals inherited their distinctive characteristic which required special needs and attention which in this case the extra-welfarist failed to address (Mooney and Russell, 2003). Further, Mooney and Russell (2003) proposed the concept of communitarian approach as the opponent to both welfarism and extra-welfarism. In the communitarian approach the decision on priority in resource allocation lies on the community perspective (the community as the central point), and not as the aggregation of utilities of individual within that community as in welfarism nor the value judgment rest on the external judgment as in extra-welfarism (as in doctors instead of patient, government instead of people). The individual freedom is not excluded from this premise, rather it is seen as part of the communal acceptance of its independence, for an individual could not function at his best unless the community (culture, norm) allow them to act in such a way. Likewise, it is also noted that the individual characteristic (both within the realm of 'capability' and 'functioning') is more or less the product that being constructed and being influenced by their community, which also an entity in itself. However, Mooney and Russell (2003) did not explicitly discuss on how to distinguish the differences between community and communal preferences, which by then would be difficult to see it being employed in a practical sense.

Whilst, the tenet of extra-welfarism, despite facing many oppositions, is currently one that had been practiced widely in health care world. The support from various governments as the user of this approach namely NICE (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence) in UK, CADTH (Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health) in Canada, PBAC (Pharmaceutical Benefit Advisory Committee) in Australia, etc., has somehow made the extra-welfarism style of analysis became increasingly prominent (Buchanan and Wordsworth, 2015; Drummond, 2004).

BASIC TYPES OF HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION

As previously said, health economic evaluation existed to measure the alternative programs by comparing each of its costs and outcomes/benefits. The differences in the outcomes (or effects) selected for the measurement unit, would determine the type of economic evaluation used (Douglas and Normand, 2005). Below, the type of health economic evaluations is explained.

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS (CBA)

CBA is using the value judgment based on the idea of the Potential Pareto Improvement (the welfarist approach) which adopting individual perspective in allocating their funding (*the willingness to pay*) for their desired outcomes (benefits/utilities) by prioritizing their chosen product (Drummond et al., 2005). The outcome here would be determined in the monetary term (Brazier et al., 2007; Drummond et al., 2005; Kobelt, 2013; McIntosh and Luengo-Fernandez, 2006; Morris et al., 2017). In defining who is the 'winner' and the 'loser', thus deciding the priority receiver for the resource allocation, CBA worked by calculating the total costs and benefits for any given product. If the 'net benefit' larger than the 'net cost' (positive) then it means that it is likely to achieve the Potential Pareto Improvement in which the total gains from the winner is somewhat larger thus compensable to the lost for the loser (Brazier et al., 2007). However, the idea of compensation mere a utopic concept, meaning that once CBA had evaluated the numerical values on which to compensate the losers, it did not continue with an explanation on how to distribute it. This 'failure' on answering crucial aspect on the distribution of goods to achieve the desired outcome for the population in its whole, became one of the reason that compelled the health economist to face away from choosing CBA to measure health outcome (Coast, 2009). Coast et al. (2008, p. 1191) identified the basic limitation of CBA (quoting Coast, 2004): first, "*is associated with distribution: by basing measurements of 'welfare' on willingness-to-pay this welfare is also affected by ability to pay and the allocation of health care*

resources could thus be 'skewed' towards the wealthy"; second, "is practical: many people in such societies are extremely uncomfortable with the notion of valuing length and quality of life in monetary term and are thus unwilling to participate in such exercise". Furthermore, Brazier et al. (2007) explained that the characteristic of CBA in valuing the health gained (benefit) in monetary term, would receive substantial resistant from the majority of public sector's institutions. Not to mention, since the basis of CBA using the welfarist approach is the willingness to pay, therefore the budget allocation would likely to be directed more to the wealthier within society, in which such circumstance despite rational, may not be acceptable.

COST-EFFECTIVENESS ANALYSIS (CEA)

When a decision maker having to deal with an inquiry regarding which, within several alternatives of programs, actually give more benefit under a very limited budget, then CEA is the type of economic analysis that being deployed to answer that (Drummond et.al, 2005; McGuire, 2001; Owens, 1998). CEA is the method in health economic evaluation "*in which cost are related to single, common effect that may differ in magnitude between the alternative programmes*" (Drummond et al., 2005, p. 12). Subsequently, "*the application of cost-effectiveness analysis follows directly from the attribution of relevant cost to relevant effects*" (McGuire, 2001, p. 11). Meaning that to make sure that the end-choice made is effective and efficient at the same time, the incremental cost per unit of the expected outcome from each of the alternatives, called Incremental Cost-effectiveness Ratio (ICERs), needs to be compared. The decision makers further listed down the ICERs from the least costly program (per unit of outcome) which represented as the most effective/efficient option, until the most unpreferable one, in the bottom of the list. It is then the decision maker's choice either to exhaust their budget from the top list until the final one or select one or several from the top and neglect the rest (McGuire, 2001). Figure 1. Depicted the calculation for CEA.

Figure 2. Calculating ICER

$$\text{Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio} = \frac{(\text{cost of drug A} - \text{cost of drug B})}{(\text{benefits of drug A} - \text{benefits of drug B})}$$
$$\text{ICER} = \frac{\text{difference in costs (A-B)}}{\text{difference in benefits (A-B)}}$$

Furthermore, to employ this analysis, the 'effect' should first be decided into 'a single unit of outcome measurement' so that each of the alternatives could then be compared. And judging that 'health' is the ultimate goal of any health treatment or health intervention, it is only rational to calculate effectiveness by comparing cost and health-related gained (the effect) as the output unit from different alternatives to later determined the priority settings. However, it is not always easy to associate the particular treatment to the final result of the health-related gained resulted from receiving such particular treatment/intervention. Therefore, in CEA, they can either employ a final outcome of health-related one as the unit of measurement or mere the intermediate value that lead to improvement of someone's health, as the measurement unit (Drummond et al., 2005). However, as the Drummond et al. (2005) reminded that the use of the intermediate value as the unit of measurement should be based on a very careful judgment and rigorous consideration. The analysts should, as he continued, able to explain how that intermediate unit has the correlation toward achieving the ultimate goal of the health-gained outcome as anticipated.

Moreover, there are several studies that used health-related gained (the final outcome) as the unit of outcome measurement. For example, in the form of 'life-years gained' or 'life-years saved' could be seen in the study of CEA in colorectal cancer screening (Frazier et al., 2000; Pickhardt, 2007; Pignone et al., 2002; Wagner et al., 1991), breast cancer screening (de Koning et al., 1991), abdominal aortic aneurysm screening (British Medical Journal Publishing Group, 2002), patients with liver cancer in determining between two types of liver transplantation, cadaveric liver transplantation versus living donor transplantation (Sarasin et al., 2001). Furthermore, the unit of (final) outcome could also be found in other forms such as: 'vision-

years gained' or 'sight-years gained' (Peeters et al., 2012; Maberley et al., 2003); 'years-free from end points' (which end points here decided as diabetes-related) as in study conducted by Raikou et al. (1998) in determining cost-effectiveness among variant of hypertensive medications for type 2 diabetic patients; 'episode-free days' in asthmatic patients (Ericsson et al., 2006); etc. Whilst, CEA studies that used intermediate values as the outcome measured could be found in the form of: 'per case-detected' as the study conducted by Wang et al. (2015) where they calculated the cost per recurrence case-detected in people with the risks for thyroid cancer, or in breast cancer screening study by Griebisch et al., (2006); 'per case-averted' in the study to compare effectiveness of HIV drugs regimen to prevent maternal-fetal transmission (Marseille et al., 1999); 'per mmHg blood pressure reduction' as conducted by Patel et al. (2014) in measuring the cost-effectiveness of drug variants of beta blockers; 'per cholesterol reduction' in the study conducted in Spain by Plans-Rubió (2006) to compute the ICERs ratio between several statins (HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors), a lowering cholesterol drugs (LDL-C lowering medication); etc. However, again, it should be reiterated that despite it is valid to use the intermediate outcome as the unit of measurement for economic evaluation, any researchers who are interested in making their study's results reliable should administer several critical reasonings as follow: *"1. Make a case for the intermediate endpoint having value or clinical relevance in its own right, 2. be confident that the link between intermediate and final outcomes has been adequately established by previous research, or 3. ensure that any uncertainty surrounding the link is adequately characterized in the economic study"* (Drummond et al., 2005, p. 109).

In summary, the economic evaluation using cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) often used to contrast between different medical or health care interventions (therapeutics, screening programs, preventive programs, etc) within the same category. By selecting the appropriate measurement unit of outcome based on the previous clinical studies, it is then allowed to be compared with the cost of several alternatives under observation, thus revealing the most

effective and/or efficient program for decision maker to choose. However, since CEA is using a single unit of outcome measured which should be similar in a way (despite different in magnitude), it would not be applicable to appraise different alternatives under different categories (Coyle and Davies, 1993), hence the cost-utility analysis (CUA) would be useful in such case.

COST-UTILITY ANALYSIS (CUA)

The role of CEA as an adequate tool to appraise the effectiveness of health care or medical intervention to inform decision makers regarding resources allocation, remained in doubt (Donaldson et al., 2002; Prosser et al., 2000). Cost-utility analysis, which almost identical to CEA (some said the extension of CEA), is further being introduced to combine both morbidity rate (quality of life) and mortality rate (quantity of life) as one unit of outcome measurement thus could surpass the inability of CEA to compare the alternatives from different categories (Coyle and Davies, 1993; Kobelt, 2013; Zweifel and Breyer, 1997). Drummond et al. (2005) pointed out more clearly the problems surrounding CEA that could be addressed better with CUA, like 1) As mentioned earlier, CEA failed to contrast between broad spectrum of health programs due to its limitation to assess variety of effects from across programs, 2) CEA could not solved the problem involving decision related to opportunity cost, in term of how to decide which program should be sacrificed under budget constraint, 3) CEA could not address the multiple possible outcomes arose from one specific program, whilst it is inevitable for any program to come with several effects/impacts or outcomes which supposedly also taken into account, 4) CEA did not qualified to grading the outcome, whilst outcomes would come with different grade and magnitude.

By definition Cost-Utility Analysis (CUA) can be explained as the “*type of economic evaluation where the effects are estimated in utility units, e.g. QALYs*” (McIntosh and Luengo-Fernandez, 2006, pp. 107), other unit of measurement is in the form of Healthy Year Equivalent (HYE), the Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) but with QALYs continued to be the most acclaimed one (Kobelt, 2013). What is QALYs? QALYs is the composite unit to measure between life years gained (the quantity) and the patient’s perspective of how that loss or gain (of life

Figure 4. Simple calculation of QALYs (taken from Ternopil State Medical University, no date)

With treatment X	Without treatment X
Estimated survival = 10 years	Estimated survival = 5 years
Estimated quality of life (relative to 'perfect health') = 0.7	Estimated quality of life (relative to 'perfect health') = 0.5
QALYs = (10 X 0.7) = 7.0	QALYs = (5 X 0.5) = 2.5
QALY gain from treatment X = 7 - 2.5 = 4.5 QALYs	
If the cost of treatment X is £18,000 then the cost per QALY is £4,000 per QALY (£18,000 divided between 4.5 additional QALY's)	

years) affected them (the quality). This is the economist answered to the CEA limitation which unable to take into account how that health-related outcome (quantity) affected people’s

Figure 3. the exponential growth of CUA

satisfaction/situation/condition (utility/quality). The idea of QALYs derived from the concept that it is possible to quantify the quality of life into a single index. And unlike in CEA, the employment of standardised unit to measure health outcomes, both in term of quality and quantity of life, allowed QALYs (CUA) to be used to compare diseases or interventions across categories or groups (Drummond et al., 2005; McPake et al., 2002; Morris et al., 2007). The QALYs is measured by weighing between how patients perceived their quality of life in various

different health states or the utility (with e.g. perfect health = 1; and death = 0) and the time spent in each health state (Goeree and Diaby, 2013).

ISSUES ON QALYS

There were many disputes surrounding QALYs as the appropriate device to assess cost-effectiveness, despite its 'fame' and the fact that it had been utilized by many governments, health economists and specialists. The United Kingdom with NICE (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence), for example, has made major impact toward the presentation and the application of QALYs as the standard metric to measure cost-effectiveness for new health technologies, thus has positioned the UK as the world's leader in this field (Pettitt et al., 2016). However, not all medical professional agreed with the use of QALYs to assess the priority for patient's treatments. A strong view against QALYs, for instance, coming from Rawles (1989), a member of FRCP (Fellowship of the Royal College of Physicians) from Aberdeen that '*castigating QALYs*' as unethical and unjust. To his remark, QALYs has undervalued life by mere scoring the quality of life based on the absence of suffering. He believed that there should be an alternative measurement addressing the patient's needs in the budget allocation setting. His protest mainly coming from the fact that QALYs was over simplifying the value of health outcome omitting the fact that several alternatives taken into QALY's equation were not equitable *per se*, as he said, "*I take particular objection to the use of QALYs for comparing the outcome of fatal and non-fatal diseases*" (Rawles and Rawles, 1990, pp. 93). In contrast, Mooney (1989) debated that Rawles' claimed regarding the doctors might know better about the patient's needs (in oppose to QALYs) must be *taken with a pinch of salt*. Mooney continued explain, that since patient mere a fraction of the whole society that they involved in, then to deploy a QALYs as the explicit and rational tool (subjected to improvement) to set a priority setting upon the finite resources correspond to the societal preferences, was only reasonable. After all, Mooney conceptual basis coming from seeing that the scarce resources are applied to

the general society in the entirety. Therefore, any rational decision makers should encompass other aspect outside health care (non-healthcare aspect) to justify their decision to allocate the constraint resources in health care, not only using the ‘patients’ standpoint but should also consider the whole construction of social welfare. Hence, to determine ‘what is the best way to allocate the resources’ should not be based on personal assumption (physician nor patient). However, Rawles was not the only one who denounced QALYs for its ethical ‘flaw’. Drummond et al. (1993, pp. 34) for example, wrote that *“there is still considerable debate concerning the appropriateness of the QALY measure, as compared with the healthy-years equivalent; the differences between the methods for eliciting values of health states (e.g. rating scale, time trade-off, and standard gamble); the likely differences in valuations of health states between different groups (e.g. doctors, patients, and the general public) and across countries; and the potential for developing generic indices, with prescaled health utility values, that would avert the need to value every health state independently”*. Accordingly, Pettitt et al. (2016) summarized the critiques in 3 common themes: 1. the ethical issues surrounding QALY’s, 2. the weakness in methodological and theoretical approaches, 3. The problem related to context (or diseases related). Nevertheless, despite all the criticisms, to date, most health economists still favour QALYs to measure cost-effectiveness to rationale the priority decision-making and none other ‘equal’ competitor had been found, so far (Goeree and Diaby, 2013; Kind and Gudex, 1993; Kobelt, 2013).

NICE AND QALYS THRESHOLD, TOO HIGH?

The National Institute and Clinical Excellence (NICE) was constituted since 1999 to provide economic evaluation guideline for UK health care decision makers (NHS) in England and Wales jurisdiction. NICE has been the ‘avid user’ of QALYs and had set the amount of £20,000 to £30,000 per QALYs gained as the threshold for any new health care programs or interventions, with the expense less than £20,000 per QALY gained is deemed to be most cost-effective (NICE, 2012). However, certain authors had raised concern that the current NICE’s

threshold is still way too high for NHS to afford (Claxton et al., 2015; Raftery, 2014). To Claxton et al. (2015) NICE threshold recommendation was overestimated, they further suggested to lower the threshold not more than approximately £13,000 per QALY. While Appleby (2016) seemed to defend NICE by saying that the threshold is 'too generous' with the threshold need to be accrued since the public 'willingness to pay' for health could be up to £70,000 (Towse, 2009); in contrast, McCabe et al. (2008) corroborated with Claxton et al. (2015) argued that the threshold should be adjusted to lower mark with a single threshold applied. However, as Towse and Pritchard (2002) pointed out NICE did not necessarily consider the cost-effectiveness alone to appraise the proposals coming. From the proposal of the use of a first-line drug, Docetaxol, for breast cancer patients to the laparoscopic procedure for patient with colorectal cancer; they all have been dropped by NICE, due to lack of clinical effectiveness evidences. Moreover, differ from its 'confidant' DQTC (Ministry of Health's Drug Quality and Therapeutics Committee) in Canada, NICE is also more selective. If DQTC regards every application for reimbursement consideration, NICE in the other hand focused more into arduous matters like "*the trade-offs between increased benefit and increased costs*" (Drummond, 2004, pp. 6). Another problem in the implementation of NICE guideline is the financial constraint faced by NHS today. For example, from the £93 million NHS expenditure per year, predicted by NICE for the recommended drugs, only one-third or approximately £32 million has been executed according to IMS report, with one possible explanation that those drugs mostly concentrated in the hospital setting whilst it implemented cost-containment with very controlled expenditures (Towse and Pritchard, 2002). Therefore, it would be interesting to see the implementation of NICE guidelines in the field, among meso-level and micro-level decision makers.

THE USE OF DECISION ANALYTIC MODELLING IN HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATIONS

The application of health economic evaluation would be bounded entirely to the availability of previous empirical studies of clinical effectiveness (especially if the measurement related to drugs or new medical treatments). However, since the necessity to devise a rational decision making regarding resources allocation continued, supplemented by a growing demand from the public for transparency in the usage of the constraint resources; the limitation in clinical evidences ought not to hinder the explicit priority assessment using economic evaluation. For this matter, health economist had created a decision modelling for economic evaluation, to assist decision makers forging a rational judgment (Douglas and Normand, 2005; Gray and Vale, 2003; Kuntz and Weinstein, 2001). It can be said, therefore, that the role of modelling in health economic evaluations is to derive with guideline for decision making under uncertainty situation (Brazier et al., 2007; Briggs et al., 2006, Goeree and Diaby, 2013; Morris et al., 2007). This modelling embedded a mathematical extrapolation from multiple sources of evidences, to further simulate the clinical experiences under probabilistic scenarios to finally derive with the unit of output like QALYs (Kuntz and Weinstein, 2001), and most common used technique is Markov model (Drummond et al., 2005; Goeree and Diaby, 2013; Morris et al., 2007). However, the use of modelling has raised some concern regarding too many assumptions employed in it (Kuntz and Weinstein, 2001). Another approach to conduct health economic evaluation is using the trial based data, as in Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT). Further, Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) had been recognized as the most dependable sources for economic evaluation (Sculpher et al., 2006), hence, often used as secondary data for systematic reviews purposes (Sheldon et al., 1993). However, it is argued that a single RCT (which commonly employed these days) could yield a comprehensive set of data needed for economic analysis (Goeree and Diaby, 2013; Sculpher et al., 2006), therefore a wide variety of study designs type should be used for economic evaluation to encompass more extensive dimensions which

in this case may derive with uncertainty therefore employing decision analytic modelling for health economic analysis is inevitable (Drummond et al., 2005; Kuntz and Weinstein, 2001).

Figure 5. Decision Analytic Modelling

Decision modelling as a tool to face the challenge

How to allocate funds between competing priorities?

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND STUDY DESIGN

STUDY DESIGN

To address the research questions, a literature review based methodology with systematic approach is chosen in this study. The systematic literature review is beneficial in term of collecting and analysing the already published and unpublished literatures in the area that this study covered, also in the attempt to give a comprehensive understanding and delivering composite evidences to answer the current research queries (Aveyard et al., 2016; Hewitt-Taylor, 2017). Moreover, conducting a systematic review is important as Aveyard (2014) wrote that trying to make an interpretation over one research would likely to arrive in irrational judgment, which would coerce to erroneous in action. Consequently, a secondary research approach, as in systematic review, is essential to analyse those former findings and further to elicit a synthesized interpretation (Gomersall et al., 2015), as explained by European Commission (2004) that judging by the complexities of the identified problems it is unlikely that a single approach would able to devise with a comprehensive solution. Therefore, by doing a systematic review, it could provide the current pictures of the topic of interest, identify the common findings and the probable gaps among studies, as well as to scrutinize the methods employed (Hewitt, 2007).

Furthermore, another reason to conduct systematic review for the purpose of this study because there was already some of researches around the impact economic evaluations in the health care decision-making process (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011; Drummond et al., 1993; Goeree and Diaby, 2013). Consequently, conducting a systematic review to critically appraise the plethora of economic evaluation literatures is deemed to be significant (Aveyard et al., 2016; Gomersall et al., 2015; Hewitt-Taylor, 2017; Sheldon et al., 1993), as to quote Mathes et al. (2014,

pp. 826) that “*to identify all relevant studies and yield valid information, a review of economic evaluations should be systematically performed*”. This is also accorded with Hewitt-Taylor (2017) when he wrote that under situation when there were abundant evidences already exist, a systematic literature review would allow the gathering of all information coming from different sources with various approaches, methodologies, and findings; and led to the formulation of somewhat the best solution from the perceived dilemmas. Hence, the researcher would be able to gain a clarity over the objects being observed and able to improve the collective comprehension on the matter which may probably still suffered from discrepancy, lack of focus and inconclusiveness. Finally, quoting Aveyard (2014, p. 3) that “*a good quality literature review is a piece of research in its own right*”, thus a systematic review is as important as a primary study employing empirical data, perhaps even better.

Additionally, aligning with the purpose of this study, the configurative approach is chosen to conduct the systematic review. Gough et al. (2012) explained that the aim of a configurative review is to develop conceptual ideas surrounding the objects of the study, by configuring and interpreting all the collected materials hence would enhance the already existing body of knowledge. In another saying, it would derive with new perspective in the apprehension of the whole confusion arose from the antecedent studies. Contrastingly, the review type using aggregative method would pursue different objective which is to produce an aggregate information from the primary empirical data that being collected thus arrived with empirical articulation. Such type of review would be deviated from the current research purposes where the researcher seeks to gain enlightenment from the current perceived problems, and to conceptualize the issues from different viewpoints in order to deliver a more comprehensive understanding. Whilst, an aggregative approach would hinder such pursuit, since its tendency to mere look the homogeneity within the studies to try reassuring their predefined hypothesis (Gough et al., 2017).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SELECTION CRITERIA

The electronic based literature searching is conducted in this study, employing a systematic search strategy to find and collect a secondary data from health economics literatures, both within category of a primary researches and secondary researches (a review) and/or a type of non-research papers, that discussed the use of health economic evaluation in health care decision making. The multiple type of literatures chosen in order to gain in-depth and comprehensive understanding over the topic under observation thence would derive with thorough answers for the research questions.

Furthermore, the literatures range of year is restricted to the search for literature that had been published within the last 10 years (from the January year of 2000 to September 2017), to keep this study up to date with the recent theory development. Subsequently, only qualitative studies were employed within this review, for it is corresponding to the research questions and the study objective. Accordingly, to derive with more focus results, studies from non-OECD countries are not included in this review. Another reason for this, because it is assumed that the studies conducted in OECD countries are comparable in nature, despite each country possessed a distinct health care system. Accordingly, due to the researcher limitations and personal conveniences, only studies that presented in English language are adopted. Moreover, since this review is intended to investigate the literatures that discussed the use of economic evaluations among local health care decision makers, therefore the literatures that covered only specific type of health economic evaluations were being excluded (for example this study did not include a literature that only discussed exclusively about CBA or CEA or CUA). Similarly, any literature that only addressed a health economic evaluation to a specific type of health technology (e.g. specific program, treatment, disease, health intervention or health service) are also excluded from this review. Further, the inclusion criteria also specific in finding the implementation of

economic evaluation among local health care decision makers, therefore any literature that did not address this matter in particular, were being excluded. Also, as the term of Health Economic Evaluation (HEE) and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) are sometime found to be coalesced in the literature, the selection criteria focused solely to the literature that discussed HEE hence, any literature that addressing HTA exclusively would be excluded. Finally, the inclusion criterion would be constrained to the literature that available in full text, since the literature which unattainable in complete version could not be appraised in-depth.

In summary, table 1. listed the inclusion and exclusion criterions

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criteria for Inclusion	
1	Study Design: Qualitative Research
2	Range of years of publication: Jan 2000 to Sept 2017
3	Language: English
4	Participants: meso/micro level (local decision makers)
Criteria for Exclusion	
1	Discussed specific type of health economic evaluation
2	HTA (Health Technology Assessment)
3	Not available in full text
4	Macro level decision makers
5	Non-OECD countries

SEARCH STRATEGY

The search for literatures is started from selecting the appropriate databases. ‘Embase’, ‘MEDLINE’ and ‘Cinahl plus’ were chosen for this matter because they covered a wide range of health-related topics, ‘Cochrane Library’ is also used to search for systematic reviews type of literatures.

Accordingly, the search was narrowed down using targeted keywords related to the purpose of this study. These keywords extracted initially from the words composition in the

main research question also guided by the ideas excerpted from the specific themes discussed in the existing literatures within similar topic of interests. Further, the relevant synonyms for a specific word or phrase or other proxy that mostly applied for the same intention, were being considered in the attempt to amplify the keywords searched to acquire more eligible evidences. For a common terminology in health economics which is formed in phrase words, quotation marks were employed to capture the desirable literatures further. However, no emphasizing was taken into singular nor plural words because all the databases have had handled such matter delicately. Later, all the corresponding words or phrases in the e-search strategy were embedded together using boolean operator “OR”, “AND”. Upon decided the appropriate keywords strategy, the same type of strategy was then applied to all the chosen databases.

Furthermore, to affirm that all the appropriate literatures were captured and also in the attempt to conduct a systematic approach to the search strategy, the keywords located in the title, abstract were scrutinized, and, if possible, the content of the literature also being examined. Subsequently, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were incorporated after the total literatures had been scrutinized and eliminated from any duplication. In addition, by following the citation from the existing literature’s references, any relevant materials were hand-searched to broaden the compilation further. Moreover, in-depth screening was conducted to conclude the findings. Finally, the end-results were used as the data for the study purposes.

The following are the list of the keywords used for the search and the structure of the composite keywords using boolean operator:

Table 2. Keywords used and boolean operator

MEDLINE/CINAHL Plus/Embase/Cochrane
((("economic evaluation") OR "economic appraisal") OR "economic analysis") OR "economic analyses"
AND
((health) OR healthcare) OR clinical) OR "health care"
AND
((((use) OR application) OR implementation) OR presentation) OR implication) OR applicabilities
AND
(((((obstacles) OR challenges) OR barriers) OR limitations) OR issues) OR problems) OR impediments) OR difficulties
AND
((decision-making) OR "decision making") OR "decision makers") OR "decision process"
FINAL KEYWORDS:
(((((("economic evaluation") OR "economic analysis") OR "economic analyses") OR "economic appraisal")) AND (((health) OR healthcare) OR health care) OR clinical)) AND (((((use) OR application) OR implementation) OR presentation) OR implication) OR applicabilities)) AND ((((((obstacles) OR challenges) OR barriers) OR limitations) OR issues) OR problems) OR impediments) OR difficulties)) AND (((decision-making) OR "decision making") OR "decision makers") OR "decision process")

In summary, the combination of the electronic databases searched and the hand-searched strategy were implemented to ensure that all the appropriate literatures for the study purposes were comprehensively captured.

DATA EXTRACTION

The title and abstract from the results of electronic database searches were screened for the relevant papers. All the pertinent findings were then extracted to EndNote X8 and further assessed for duplication. Both inclusion and exclusion criteria were employed subsequently. The remaining data, already retrieved in full text, then compiled to spreadsheets using Microsoft Excel 2016. The findings further grouped into 3 different categories, namely: a research type of paper which then divided into a primary research and a review; and a non-research type of paper. For each category, the material further classified and deducted according to general information (author, title, year, geographic) and study characteristics (research question, aim/objective, methodology, participants, research finding, author

conclusion/recommendation). For non-research type of papers, a slight adjustment to the above criteria was applied. After read and re-read the full contents of the literatures to implement in-depth screening to find the appropriate sources to answer this study research questions, several literatures found to serve the purposes and further appraised.

DATA APPRAISAL

To appraise the quality of the studies, the critical appraisal tool taken from CASP (Critical Appraisal Skills Program) was used, which provided the critical appraisal checklist for qualitative research study and systematic review (Appendix I and Appendix II). Critical appraisal is *“the structured assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each paper to enable you to make an assessment as to the relevance of the paper to your own literature review question”* (Aveyard, 2014, p. 104). Doing critical appraisal is crucial to evaluate the quality and the validity of the study, to make sure that the data taken for this systematic review were rigorously selected (Aveyard et al., 2016; Hewitt-Taylor, 2017; Katrak, et al. 2004; Munn et al., 2014). While as for choosing to conduct the critical appraisal using the critical appraisal tool, it would not only help to ease an amateur (Aveyard, 2014) such as the researcher of this paper, but also to reassure that the review of the literatures is thorough and well-structured therefore managed to identify all the relevant findings (Hewitt-Taylor, 2017). Although there is no gold standard for critical appraisal tool (Katrak et al., 2004), it is advised to choose a recognized tool for this purpose (Aveyard, 2014) and CASP is one of them, as recommended by several authors (Aveyard, 2014; Aveyard et al., 2016; Hewitt-Taylor, 2017).

DATA SYNTHESIS

Thematic synthesis is chosen for the purpose of our study. Aveyard et al. (2016, p. 129-130) summarised the steps for thematic synthesis' approach as follow:

“identifying a research question, purposive searching, aiming for conceptual saturation rather than a comprehensive inclusion of all literatures, quality appraisal, recognizing the complexity of this, identifying key concepts in individual studies, developing codes and themes for the key concepts, checking of consistency of coding/themes between the different studies, translating concepts into one another, generating themes; third order interpretation”.

The researcher followed each step as purposed in the above statement, to ensure that this study is conducted in systematic and rigorous manners.

CHAPTER IV RESULTS

DATABASES SEARCH FINDING

A structured and systematic electronic literatures search strategy was executed in 12 September 2017. In total, 2191 literatures from various databases were derived from the initial phase of electronic searched using the targeted keywords. Upon finished scrutinizing the title and abstract for the relevant keywords and contexts, 110 literatures remained for the next examination. These data then extracted to EndNote X8 to employ further screening and filter, to collect the appropriate findings. In exact 25 literatures were being subtracted for duplication. The rest then subjected for further inclusion and exclusion based on the already set criterions. The 19 full papers collected so far, subject to further in-depth study by being read and re-read for relevant materials pertinent to the current study purposes. There were 6 papers, afterward, being subtracted which disaccord to the study objectives. Subsequently, 3 more literatures were added by hand searched following the citation from the previous findings. Finally, in total 16 literatures matched the study criterions and further appraised and analysed.

Figure 6. Summarized the results.

Figure 6. flow diagram of search results and data extraction

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FINDINGS

There were three types of literatures compiled for the study purposes: 1) Research type of data, which then categorized into: 1.1. Primary research 1.2. Systematic Review; 2) Non-research type of data as showed in table 3.

Table 3. summary of the type of literatures

Research Papers (n= 9)		Non-research Papers (n= 5)
Primary Qualitative Papers (n= 7)	Systematic Reviews (n = 2)	
Eddama and Coast, 2009	Eddama and Coast, 2008	Brousselle and Lessard, 2011
Hoffmann et al., 2002	Erntoft, 2011	Buxton, 2005

Hoffmann and Graf von der Schulenburg, 2000		Drummond, 2004
Roseboom et al., 2015		Lessard et al., 2010
Williams et al., 2008		Van Gool et al., 2007
Wu et al., 2004		
Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000		

PRIMARY RESEARCH PAPERS

For type of primary research papers, the jurisdiction in which the empirical studies took place, were being compiled separately, while also taken note on the existing of a regulatory body (if existed), similar like NICE in UK, in that particular country (source taken from Franken et al., 2016; Mathes et al., 2013). Accordingly, the type of health care funding taken from 4 basic models by T.R. Reid (Frontline, 2015), namely the Beveridge model, the Bismarck model, the National Health Insurance Model, the Out-of-Pocket model, were also being considered, to examine and classify the type of health care system that each country has adopted. While for the source of information regarding each country's health care system was taken from CESifo DICE Report (2008) and the study by Franken et al. (2016).

From all six studies, three of the studies were discussing the issues specific for UK settings, while two of them were specific around the Netherland's health care settings, whilst only one major study was addressing and comparing the issues from multiple European countries (including UK). The UK and the Netherlands adopted different health care system, namely Beveridge and Bismarck, respectively. Likewise, all 8 different countries in the study conducted by Hoffmann and Graf von der Schulenburg (2000) they all adopting either Beveridge or Bismarck type of health care system (funding). Furthermore, all of these countries have a regulation body in macro level (Franken et al., 2016; Mathes et al., 2013) which deals with the formulation of guideline for the application of health economic evaluation either for reimbursement strategy, drugs formulary adoption procedure, or health care technologies

appraisal system (Hjelmgren et al., 2001;), almost corresponding with the existence of NICE in UK.

Table 4. showed the listing.

Table 4. summary geography and health care system (primary research papers)

LITERATURES	GEOGRAPHY	HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION BODIES (MACRO LEVEL)	HEALTH CARE SYSTEM
EDDAMA AND COAST, 2009	England (UK)	NICE	Beveridge ⁵
HOFFMANN ET AL., 2002	United Kingdom (UK)	NICE	Beveridge
HOFFMANN AND GRAF VON DER SCHULENBURG, 2000	Finland, Spain, Austria, Germany, Norway, Portugal, France, Netherlands, UK	Pharmaceutical Price Board, the ISCIII, GOEG, IQWiG, Norwegian Medicines Agency, INFARMED, Commission de Transparence (CdT), ZIN, NICE (respectively)	Beveridge, Beveridge, Bismarck, Bismarck, Beveridge, Bismarck, Bismarck, Bismarck, Beveridge (respectively)
ROSEBOOM ET AL., 2015	Netherlands	ZIN	Bismarck ⁶
WILLIAMS ET AL., 2008	UK	NICE	Beveridge
WU ET AL., 2004	Scotland (UK)	NICE	Beveridge
ZWART-VAN RIJKOM ET AL., 2000	Netherlands	ZIN	Bismarck

Moreover, there was one study conducted by Hoffmann et al., 2002 that used focus groups purposefully selected from two health care authorities in England, UK, namely Leicestershire and North Yorkshire and as for Roseboom et al. (2015), they conducted a study using interview only; whilst Wu et al. (2004) chose the qualitative approach using solely postal and email questionnaires. The most interesting study was from Williams et al. (2008) which employed a thorough research using the combination of a literature review and empirical study method (however since mostly that the methods used by them were empirical in nature, therefore for the current study purpose, study by Williams et al. (2008) was being classified as primary research type paper). The rest of the studies utilized multiple methods from interview

⁵ The Beveridge system was first introduced in 1942 in UK, and named after Sir William Henry Beveridge, is a tax-funded health care system.

⁶ The Bismarck is a Statutory health care system (SHI) founded by Oto von Bismarck in 1883, in a form of insurance system which mostly co-funded between employers and employee but unprofitable in nature. It also must universally coverage in its extend.

to observation or interview and questionnaires. The detailed of the study designs employed summarized in the table 5. below.

Table 5. the characteristics of primary research papers

LITERATURES	TIMELINE	METHODS	PARTICIPANTS	AIMS/OBJECTIVE
EDDAMA AND COAST, 2009	January 2003 to April 2004	in-depth interviews, observation and documents analysis	20 interviewees, 13 meetings (10-15 members)	to explore the views/opinions of health care decision makers in England about the use of HEE
HOFFMANN ET AL., 2002	February and April 2000	Focus groups	4 meetings (14 participants in total from 2 different UK health authorities + chairperson from each health authorities	to understand further the use of HEE among NHS professionals and whether accessibility to the HEE studies would be favourable
HOFFMANN AND GRAF VON DER SCHULENBURG, 2000		postal questionnaire survey, semi-structured interviews and focus group	questionnaire: total 968 participants, 53 interviews, 20 focus groups (from multiple countries)	to evaluate the decision makers perspective in term of: knowledge of HEE, the use of HEE, the attitudes toward HEE, and the barriers and incentives of using HEE
ROSEBOOM ET AL., 2015	April and June 2014	semi-structured and structured interviews	18 participants comprised of: 16 Dutch health care decision makers and 2 health economists	to provide information on the use of HEE among health care decision makers in Netherlands and evaluated the existing barriers and facilitators
WILLIAMS ET AL., 2008	(review: literatures up to 2004) Case studies: N/A	Combination of literature reviews, local decision information pro formas and case study methods using: ● documentary analysis ● observation ● semi-structured interviews	- Literature Reviews: 1 systematic review and 27 research papers - local research: *using pro formas: 106 pro formas from secondary care and 70 from primary care *case studies: 11 meetings; 31 people interviewed *2 workshops: 15 participants (primary care, secondary care, and 1 mental health trust) - NICE research: in total 14 meetings were observed for 7 different case appraisal topics (2 meeting for each) - 30 Interviews All participants coming from members from 4 health care committees across England and Wales which also represented both national and local	to review previous HEE studies regarding its influence in decision making process, evaluated the use of local level decision makers in NHS, assessed the use of HEE in national level (NICE) and how HEE affected the decision-making process in national level, explored the opinion of decision makers about increasing the impact of HEE (accessibility and acceptability), created recommendation for the use of HEE for NHS decision makers

			decision makers and primary/secondary health care providers; and 1 NICE committee	
WU ET AL., 2004		postal and email questionnaires	27 GPs	to examine the GP's point a view on using HEE during clinical decision-making process
ZWART-VAN RIJKOM ET AL., 2000	late 1998 to early 1999	semi-structured interviews and postal questionnaires	19 interviewees, 15 surveyed participants	to investigate the perceptions, attitudes and knowledge on HEE among health care decision makers in Netherland, and the actual use of HEE also compared the result with the study by Hoffmann and Graf von der Schulenburg, 2000 (for Netherland).

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PAPERS

All of the systematic review papers that had been collected for this study purposed were taken sample of the studies from vast majority of western countries. The databases utilized were varied between these two studies but both used Econlit and WoS as their sources. Nonetheless, all papers discussed the use of health economic evaluation in local decision making, with Enrtoft (2011) also touched the issues surrounding the implementation of health economic evaluation in the macro level. Table... provided the summary of the characteristic findings in the systematic reviews papers.

Table 6. summary of the characteristic of systematic reviews

Literatures	Timeline of the adopted studies	Aims/Objectives	Databases (Data sources)	Papers Included	Geography covered	Level of decision makers
Eddama and Coast, 2008	30 years period (until 2008)	to examine whether the multiple study results (from different timeline and jurisdiction) blend in, as well as evaluated the barriers and incentives for the use of HEE and recognized any gaps between studies	MEDLINE, EMBASE, EconLit, Web of Science (WoS)	40	US (majority), UK, Australia and Europe (Netherlands, Sweden, Germany, Finland, Portugal, France, Norway, Austria, and Spain)	Local level
Erntoft, 2011	1990 and May 2009	to assess the priority setting in decision making process related to pharmaceutical, assessed the barriers and the contextual use of HEE in pharmaceutical priority settings	PubMed, EconLit, Cochrane, Web of Science, CINAHL, PsycINFO	31	US, UK, Canada, Australia Sweden, France, Germany, Netherlands, Greece	Macro, meso, micro level

NON-RESEARCH PAPERS

The non-research papers were also being collected for this systematic review purpose. They all written by health economists discussing the use and the potential barriers of the health economic evaluations on decision-making. Table 7. listed the summary.

Table 7. summary of non-research papers

Literatures	Main Topic	Jurisdiction	Conclusion
Brousselle and Lessard, 2011	Discussed the barriers to the use of health economic evaluation in decision-making. The authors also exploring the alternatives type of health economic evaluation which presumably fit more with the decision maker's needs.	General	The need to produce new paradigm in health economic evaluation that well-grounded with decision makers perspective.
Buxton, 2005	Reviewed the implication of NICE guideline among UK health care decision makers	UK	The author suggested that health economist should make an effort to understand further the decision makers context and constraint.
Drummond, 2004	Discussed the use of economic studies for health care decision makers in macro and local level. Identified the barriers to extend the use of the economic studies.	General (but mostly discussed UK setting)	The usefulness of health economic studies is doubtful (although since the author is an economist, such conclusion may purposefully motivational in nature, to induce improvement in health economic studies)
Lessard et al., 2010	Discussed the possible reason behind the limited impact of health economic evaluation studies among family physician (GP) and suggested an approach to understand the barriers using Bourdieu's theory	General (but mostly taken Canada setting)	Suggested the adoption of Bourdieu's theory to understand the constraint use of health economic evaluation in clinical decision-making (among family physician specifically)
Van Gool et al., 2007	Discussed the barriers existed among Australian local decision makers in implementing health economic evaluation in their decision-making process.	Australia	Suggested that further studies needed to extend the potential use of health economic evaluation for decision-making.

CRITICAL APPRAISAL

PRIMARY RESEARCH PAPER

Most of the studies were being evaluated as good quality according to the checklist used to appraise the study quality by CASP. Although study by Zwart-van Rijkom et al. (2000) was

not addressing the ethical concern properly, but overall the study had been conducted in structured and rigorously; it was able to relate accordingly between the objectives of the study, the method chosen to address the research questions along with the recommendation provided at the end of the study. Contrastingly, study by Wu et al. (2004) was questionable in term of the quality. They failed to justify their findings based on the study design employed (postal/mail questionnaires), although as the author remarked, that it was still useful as preliminary study to encourage next researches in similar ‘point of interests’. The detailed of critical appraisal conducted for all of the papers are expressed in table 8.

Table 8. CASP qualitative research checklist (appendix I)

Literatures	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10
Eddama and Coast, 2009	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	The study is valuable because it compiled multiple views from multiple local decision makers.
Hoffmann et al., 2002	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	The only study that used solely focus groups for data collection, which able to provide more in-depth understanding toward how the practice of decision making among health actors
Hoffmann and Graf von der Schulenburg, 2000	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	This is a very important study because it was the first major study that intended to assess decision makers attitude on health economic evaluation and the use of it in decision making process from 8 different countries (including UK)
Roseboom et al., 2015	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	This study was well-prepared and the authors mentioned thorough strategies to tackle the barriers existed
Williams et al., 2008	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	This study employed a combination of research method: systematic review and case studies. It is very valuable in providing the most comprehensive results to address the study aims
Wu et al., 2004	yes	yes	can't tell	yes	no	can't tell	can't tell	no	can't tell	Although it might be argued that the method used wasn't appropriate enough to answer the research question, but the study as the authors mentioned could be valuable enough as preliminary study
Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	can't tell	yes	yes	Although the study was assessing the use of health economic evaluation in a particular country (the Netherlands) but the findings were consistent with other similar studies (from different jurisdictions)

SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS

Both systematic reviews are beneficial in their findings which helped to provide a thorough information regarding the use of health economic evaluation and the barriers of the implementation as part of their aims/objective. The search strategy for both papers had been employed systematically and rigorously. Table 9 listed the result of critical appraisal using CASP checklist for qualitative systematic review type of literatures.

Table 9. CASP critical checklists for systematic reviews (appendix II)

Literatures	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10
Eddama and Coast, 2008	yes	yes	yes	can't tell	yes	The authors used subthemes to categorise their findings. They classified the barriers in the use of economic evaluation within local health care decision making into 3 main categories: 1. institutional and political factors, 2. cultural barriers, and 3. methodological issues	The results were precise enough, taken from 40 included papers from various countries (majority from US) with long range of published years (from 1982 until 2007).	yes	yes	yes
Erntoft, 2011	yes	yes	yes	can't tell	yes	The authors described the use and the barriers of using health economic evaluation in decision making from 3 different level: major, meso, and micro	The findings from the data taken within 10 years interval (1990s-2000s) were consistent with other recent studies	can't tell	yes	yes

THE USE OF ECONOMIC EVALUATION IN LOCAL HEALTH CARE DECISION MAKING

The implementation of economic evaluation in local health care decision making varied between meso level health care decision makers and micro level decision makers. Observation made on the PCT (Primary Care Trust, a meso level decision makers in UK) found that the PCT decided to follow NICE guidance to fund the cancer drugs as recommended, notwithstanding with the local budget constraint (Eddama and Coast, 2009). At local NHS committees across England and Wales, Williams et al. (2008) found that the Priorities Network has modestly utilized the studies of health technologies appraisal using economic analysis in compare to other committees as the participant of that study. Whilst the result from the interviewed among

GPs, from the study by Eddama and Coast (2009) revealed that majority of them seldom read published papers in health economic evaluation let alone adopted the findings into daily clinical decision-making. Contrastingly, the GPs (micro level) who were approached through postal and email questionnaire in Scotland admitted that they had employed economic evaluation consideration in their prescribing procedure (Wu et al., 2004).

Nevertheless, Drummond (2004) stated that there were only few decision makers had cost-effectiveness as their decision-making criterions. Study by Eddama and Coast (2008) and Erntoft (2011) concluded that regardless the decision makers acknowledged the importance to adopt some form of economic analysis in decision making process, the extend of the application of health economic evaluation in practice still limited. Correspondingly, research conducted by Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg found that there was a moderate use of economic evaluation among 8 countries' (UK, Finland, Spain, Austria, Germany, Norway, Portugal, France, Netherlands) local health care decision makers. Likewise, Buxton (2016) identified that UK health care decision makers showed unwillingness to follow NICE guideline.

THE BARRIERS TO UTILIZE THE HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATION INTO DECISION MAKING PROCESS

Furthermore, most of the studies in this review have collected significant data surrounding the barriers that caused the limited use of health economic evaluation in local health care decision making process. Zwart-van Rijkom et al. (2000), for instance, had asked their respondent, Dutch local health care decision makers, to put a rank in order for the perceived barriers that impede them to use the result of economic analysis study in their decision process. All of the respondents that consist of physicians, hospital pharmacists, regulators, and politicians have ranked rigidity in the budgets policy as the most perceived barriers in their practice. The inflexibility of health care budget had also been expressed by UK local health care decision makers (Eddama and Coast, 2008) and Dutch local health care decision makers (Roseboom et al., 2017), likewise the same results found in the study among

European health care decision makers (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000). This type of institutional barrier, as van Gool et al. (2007) called it 'budget silo', would deter the application of economic analysis, despite the decision makers presumably willing to take the action, because it is difficult to reallocate the budget from previous programs to a new one, or like the one perceived in NHS UK, it is not easy to move the funding from, just say, a secondary care provider to a primary care provider. Interestingly, as it expressed by NHS decision makers as the participant in study conducted by Eddama and Coast (2009) that despite NICE guideline to fund new drugs somewhat compulsory, and the decision makers feared public demand for availability would jeopardize their positions, it is their concern that NHS did not possess enough capital to fund such high cost medicine. One of the GP who was being interviewed said that they struggled to follow the NICE recommendation with their current lack of funding, despite, as another GP said, the decision made at the end determined by how much capitals they have in their saving. Correspondingly, US decision makers admitted that they found difficult to borrow the future resources to fund the current health technology, whilst economic evaluation ought to efficiently save funding for long term usage (Eddama and Coast, 2008). Another institutional barrier that coexisted with budget inflexibility, is the lack of 'incentives to treat' to implement health economic analysis as priority setting agenda in local health care (Roseboom et al., 2017). The authors suggested, as the study was administered in Netherlands setting, that the 'fee-for-service' model should be shifted to 'fee-for-performance' like currently implemented in the US health care system. It is thought that this way would be a good driver for physician to adopt health economic analysis into their consideration when deciding the appropriate treatment for their patients.

The cultural barrier seems to emerge more among micro level decision makers i.e. among physician who held responsibility in direct patients care. Many physicians have expressed their fear and resistance to endorse the use of economic analysis in their daily decision-making because to their concern, it may jeopardize the patient-doctor relationship or

it said to be unethical in approach (Eddama and Coast, 2009; Lessard et al., 2010; Roseboom et al., 2017). Most of physicians are taken clinical efficacy and safety as their main factor in deciding what best for their patients (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Eddama and Coast, 2008). Similarly, the Scotland GPs who were the participants in Wu et al. (2004) study believed that incorporating economic evaluation in their clinical decision making would be a hurdle. Other GP in different study even thought that it may break their Hippocratic Oath (Roseboom et al., 2017). However, lack of knowledge in health economics also the major barriers existed among both meso and micro level decision makers. Some participants in study by Eddama and Coast (2009) have an understanding that health economic studies mere rehearsing monetary issue, while other thought it related to study about epidemiology. Accordingly, when both politicians and physicians were asked the difference between CEA and CUA, none among them able to provide the satisfying answers (Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Whilst, participants in study by Hoffmann et al. (2002) uttered their confusion in several terminologies often used in the health economic studies, for their unfamiliar with such; and in Roseboom et al. (2017), the participants perceived difficulty in interpreting outcome unit like QALYs.

Nevertheless, methodological flaws in economic studies also conceived to be a hindrance to the extensive usage of health economic evaluation in decision making, although Erntoft (2011) concluded that it might be minor one. Some participants, for example, addressed their concern toward the quality and validity of the published economic studies. The industry funded study is one of the concern emitted among several decision makers, for it could lead to study bias (Hoffmann et al., 2002; Roseboom et al., 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Likewise, the use of economic decision-modelling which incorporated plenty of assumptions in the economic studies forged a doubt among local decision makers (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011; Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Roseboom et al., 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000).

Moreover, the issues on transferability⁷ and generalizability⁸ of economic studies also among the most common barriers disclosed by participants of the studies. In term of transferability, participants in the study by Roseboom et al. (2017) for instance, were in doubt whether QALYs would work in measuring *quid pro quo* between preventive and curative care. In the same study, participants also thought that the concept of modelling in economic studies may simplify the real situation whereas health care is a complex setting. Correspondingly, participants in Hoffmann et al. (2002) study thought that most of economic evaluation is made for a very specific context while the decision makers dealt with much convoluted issues. Subsequently, the utilitarian approach embedded in the economic studies where societal or general public perspective were the one employed in the study, thought to be irrelevant with the local problems or the contemporary issues (Buxton, 2016; Eddama and Coast, 2009; Roseboom et al., 2017, van Gool et al., 2007). Another affair that related to transferability of the economic studies is timeliness matter. Decision makers were often strained to execute decision within short term, while the economic evaluation to help overcome the issue not yet available (Eddama and Coast, 2008; Roseboom et al., 2017). Moreover, the problem with generalizability of the economic studies caused concern that it would not be easy to deploy results from different jurisdictions. Several issues might influence such finding, like Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000) admitted that currently, there were not enough studies that employing international comparability between study results. Likewise, other participants pointed out that the cost and other economic-related data were varied extensively among countries therefore it would be difficult to adopt studies conducted from a distinct geography (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011; Roseboom et al., 2017). Whilst, Eddama and Coast (2008) suggested that variation in health care

⁷ Transferability is “the process of other people transferring experimental results to real life” (www.statisticshowto.com).

⁸ Generalizability is “a measure of how well a researcher thinks their experimental results from a sample can be extended to the population as a whole” (www.statisticshowto.com).

system adopted by each country or setting may also be the cause of low generalizability of health economic study.

THE SOLUTIONS AS REVEALED IN THE STUDIES

Despite the authors realized that health economics study and its impact on decision-making process are complex nature, there were some solutions being purposed to tackle the issues. For example, judging that almost unanimously that there were evidences from all across country under studied that many decision makers have inadequate knowledge of health economic evaluation, therefore proper training or educating the decision makers to get them more acquaintance to this notion were suggested (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Hoffmann et al., 2002; Roseboom et al., 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). As a matter of fact, Roseboom et al. (2017) thought that it is also important to embed the study into medical curriculum, while at the same time emphasized the need to educate general public to cope with public resistance. It is also thought to be important to give the appropriate incentives to the decision makers, in particular frontline physician, to make use the economic evaluation studies into their priority decision-making more. Shifting from 'fee-for-service' system to 'fee-for-performance' techniques considered to be a good step (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Roseboom et al., 2017). While Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000) and Hoffmann et al. (2002) also suggested that health economists need to be employed in the decision maker bodies or engaged in a strategic position so that they could integrate more with other decision makers and hopefully bring positive influence against the current negative attitudes toward health economics studies. In fact, Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000) believed that decision makers should be asked to involve to a greater extend in the research process.

Furthermore, to decrease the study bias and to increase the quality and validity of the economic studies itself, it is crucial to make the study more transparent and credible (Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Additionally, Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg also wrote that

standardization might be appropriate to tackle the issue of generalizability and to increase the quality of the studies. Nevertheless, the dissemination of the published study to reach the decision makers or the accessibility to high quality results, should also be increased. For example, in one study suggested that it is particularly important to create a formal database that helped the decision makers to easily access high standard economic studies like in UK NHS EED, NHS Economic Evaluation Database (Roseboom et al., 2017), although other study revealed that UK NHS EED still need further improvement (Hoffmann et al., 2002). Other factor like improving the topics coverage to be further aligned with the local needs by using decision maker perspective instead of relying mere in societal perspective, had also been mentioned (Eddama and Coast, 2009; Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Roseboom et al, 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Other authors also considered other form of economic evaluation that presumably suitable with the needs of the decision makers like cost-consequences study (Hoffmann et al., 2002) or PBMA (Programme Budget Marginal Analysis), which is act more as an economic approach to health instead of part of the health economic evaluation (Eddama and Coast, 2009).

CHAPTER V DISCUSSION

Several studies had been conducted to discover the extend use of health economic studies in decision-making process in local level. This review focussed to investigate the use of health economic evaluation among local level decision makers, which local level is defined as “*where many different decisions are made by various actors within the health care system itself*” (Drummond, 2004, pp. 4) or as local level could further distinguish into meso-level and micro-level, as Erntoft (2011, pp. 587) explained that “*meso-level decision makers are involved in decisions that are oriented inside health care organizations, for example, formulary decisions or the development of local clinical guidelines*”, while as for micro-level, it “*covers the activities of individual prescribers at the patient level*”.

This review has limitation because the researcher is not a health economist, however by combining the data taken from multiple type of studies (empirical studies, systematic reviews and non-research papers) it is expected that the knowledge gap could be covered, especially by embedding this review with the articles and theories which were written by several prominent figures in health economics field. Another limitation was the time constraint which impede the researcher to cover long range of published years and the range of databases usage. However, the researcher believed that the current papers employed in this review could represent the other similar papers which discussed the same topic. Furthermore, the systematic search strategy deployed in this study could justified the appropriate findings and comprehensive review. Although, it is crucial to extend the study to exert more data from across geography to discover the similarity and sought for composite conclusions. Single authorship, also another noticeable disadvantage, with the possible study bias derived from it. To balance this, the involvement of the researcher’s supervisor who is an economist maybe perceived as an advantage.

Nevertheless, although most of the studies were deploying a qualitative approach to understand in-depth the decision makers' views and opinions, not all the authors had engaged in a suitable method. For example, study by Wu et al. (2004) relied on questionnaires alone with probable participants' bias selection, therefore the findings were questionable. As explained by Zwart-van Rijkom (2000) that interview methods most seemingly more superior compare to questionnaire in regard to certain situation like: a. the researchers constrained comprehension toward the issues or clueless on the expected responses, b. samples are limited, c. participants most likely to be uncooperative to answer the questionnaire due to their other previous engagements, d. and lastly, if the researchers are interested in gathering in-depth understanding around participant's views or opinions in which the data would be based on qualitative approach. Contrastingly, only study conducted by Williams et al. (2008) that had employed multiple methods to arrive with rigorous and all-inclusive results, although since the study was exclusive for UK decision makers, it is arguable whether the findings could be generalized elsewhere. Whilst, despite the countries under studied possessed different health care structures and systems (like some is Beveridge, and the rest is Bismarck), the evidences from the field somewhat supporting one another. For instance, studies conducted in Netherland (Roseboom et al, 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000) and UK (Eddama and Coast, 2009; Hoffmann et al., 2002) had arrived with almost similar findings regarding the decision makers views about health economic evaluations and the degree of their willingness to apply the results in their settings. Subsequently, the study that cover wide range of geographical areas like the one conducted by Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000) is pivotal to discover international comparability and at the end could derive with the establishment of standardization of health economics studies that would increase the study's generalizability beyond jurisdictions.

THE ACTUAL USE OF ECONOMIC EVALUATIONS IN LOCAL HEALTH CARE DECISION MAKING

There seems to be a consistent finding among all the papers reviewed. Almost every study concluded that there was an existence of limited use of the economic evaluation among local health care decision makers from all the jurisdictions under observation (Drummond, 2004; Eddama and Coast, 2008; Erntoft, 2011; Hoffmann et al., 2002; Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Lessard et al., 2010; Roseboom et al, 2017, van Gool et al., 2007). In UK, for example, despite major influence from NICE in providing the guideline for economic evaluation for priority settings (Buxton, 2006; Hoffmann et al., 2002; Williams et al., 2008), PCT (Primary Care Trust) in England, a meso level decision maker, felt reluctant to follow NICE recommendation for new cancer treatments, despite at the end PCT decided to subsidize the drugs anyway (Eddama and Coast, 2009). In another study, participants from focus groups observed by Hoffmann et al. (2002) admitted that they have employed an economic analysis into their decision-making considerations whilst at the same time pointed out their resistant toward the application of economic evaluation in daily practice. This conflicting finding could be explained from the selection of the participants in which they were all selected based on their willingness to participate thus could resulted in the study bias or overestimation. Similarly, recent study conducted by Roseboom et al. (2017) among Dutch health care decision makers found that some of the interviewees confessed that they have employed a form of economic analysis in their decision process in which the authors acknowledged that the small numbers of sample study and the selection bias from the health care authority might affect this result. Likewise, the low response rate from the study (44%) and the employment of participants (GPs who are members of the West of Scotland Primary Care Research and Development Network, WestNet) who showed interest to participate could overestimate the findings in which all the respondents reported that economic analysis had an impact in their clinical decisions (Wu et al., 2004). Nonetheless, there were evidences that the existence of national reimbursement

agency like the one in UK and Netherland will increase the uptake of health economics results for decision-making consideration compare to countries where similar bodies were non-existence like in Germany and France (Erntoft, 2011). The same author also assumed that the lack of utilization of health economics studies might be due to insufficient number, if not to say 'null', of health economist being employed in the setting. It is therefore arguable whether direct involvement of health economists in meso-level would bring compelling values, as recommended by Hoffmann et al. (2002) and Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000).

THE BARRIERS AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS TO INCREASE THE UPTAKE OF THE HEALTH ECONOMIC EVALUATIONS INTO DECISION MAKING PROCESS

Furthermore, all of the studies have recognized several barriers that impede the uptake of economic evaluation as part of decision making consideration especially in micro level (physicians). Hitherto, the barriers will be classified into two main themes: 1) Extrinsic barriers which coming from the impediments from the users' limitation or the one coming from institutional/political barriers, 2) Intrinsic barriers coming from the limitation of the economic evaluation studies itself. Both barriers will be discussed according to the perspective (opinions and views) of the users.

EXTRINSIC BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS

RESOURCES CONCERNED

Some of the findings had confirmed that local decision makers often faced with resources constraint (budget, skilled labours, knowledge) to be able to execute the economic evaluation in their priority-setting decisions. Budget inflexibility, for instance, caused difficulty in moving the budget from previous program to the new one, despite the result of economic evaluation showed that the new program would be more cost-effective, as it experienced particularly among hospital decision makers (Eddama and Coast, 2008; van Gool et al., 2007). In meso-level, local authorities or local health care institutions sometime found it problematic

to shift the tight budget from one particular health care institution to another, like from secondary to primary setting despite the government agenda to enhance preventive care (Roseboom et al., 2017). Similarly, the same matter had also been expressed by participants from various European countries as in the study conducted by Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg (2000). This budget silos correlated significantly with the budget constraint and government austerity policy (Buxton, 2006) in which paradoxically is one the main reason that gave birth to health economics studies in the first place. It is unsure, therefore, whether the lack of willingness to use economic studies to rationale the decision-making process was impede by the rigidity of the health care financial structure, or it was simply due to the lack of decision makers' understanding of the importance of economic studies in producing cost-effectiveness decisions. Nevertheless, strong government support in the form of the right incentives, funding, and national guidelines, are needed if health economic evaluations expected to spur and implemented consistently in decision-making process (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011). As Buxton (2006, pp. 1140) wrote that *"if as economist, we would like to see what, in terms of cost effectiveness, is a more rational allocation of spending at a local level, we need to be actively arguing for less perverse budgetary arrangements rather than passively criticising local behaviour"*, further he added that an economist *"have to argue for more economically logical budgetary and financial incentives, and find ways of reconciling these with understandable desire to have clear systems of managerial control and oversight"*.

KNOWLEDGE AND TRAINING

Moreover, the majority of the participants agreed that engaging in economic evaluation for health care prioritization is pivotal (Hoffmann et al, 2002; Roseboom et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2004). However, this was not correlated with the fact that most of them unable to explain the exact meaning of what health economic evaluation is. For example, despite 63% respondents from macro and meso-level revealed that they had received some formal health economic

evaluation trainings, but the majority of them failed to describe the type of health economic evaluations and regarded the analysis mere related to the cost consideration alone (Roseboom et al., 2017). Correspondingly, the physicians and the politicians who were interviewed by Zwart-van Rijkom et al. (2000) had trouble to distinguish the difference between CEA and CUA. While in the study by Eddama and Coast (2009) the GPs participants still confused in associating the term cost and effect. Similarly, participants in a study by Hoffmann et al. (2002) found the health economics terminologies are arduous. The lack of participants knowledge could also be seen as the explanation behind why most of them showed their reluctant to implant the economic evaluation studies in the priority-settings. The GPs, in particular, almost uniformly mentioned how economic evaluations would disrupt their relationship with the patients, while also emphasizing their priority decisions based on the efficacy and safety (Eddama and Coast, 2009; Roseboom et al., 2017). However, what they seem failed to understand that irrational decision making may jeopardize their patients' health (Eddama and Coast, 2009). Therefore, van Gool et al. (2007) believed that improving decision makers understanding over health economic principles would increase their acceptance and lead to the increase in the uptake of economic evaluation in decision-making. The question so forth, what sort of training is appropriate for this purpose? Since several studies reported that these decision makers had confessed that they already engaged with some former of health economics' trainings (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000), would it be possible then that the former trainings ineffective in changing the decision makers perspective or inadequate to inform them the appropriate comprehension about the role of health economic evaluation in decision making? Despite, this required further study, van Gool et al. (2007) suggested that inadequate knowledge from the decision makers side could be tackled by providing a 'user-friendly' and more explicit explanation about the methodological approach thus could settle the most common misunderstanding and suspicion regarding the quality and the validity of economic studies as well as to raise the decision makers awareness on its importance. Accordingly,

respondents in the Roseboom et al. (2017) study added that public training for the same purposes could also be beneficial, as it leads to public acceptance, especially acknowledging that for a public funded health care system, the whole population is equally contributing to financing the system, therefore all have the rights for information as well as the rights to participate. Another worth to consider is to employ more health economists in the decision-making bodies and to embrace the decision makers in the research process to capture the factual situations (Erntoft, 2011; Hoffmann et al., 2002; Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000). Lastly, a current quote from Drummond (2004, pp. 8) is valuable to reflect, *“if decision makers rejecting economic evaluation as a basis for their decisions, they owe it to us to be more explicit about their decision-making criteria. Certainly, explicitness is one attribute of economic evaluation that is not very apparent in most health care decision making contexts”*.

LACK OF INCENTIVES FOR DECISION MAKERS

Most of front-line decision makers (physicians both working in secondary and primary care), who have to deal directly with patients, need further booster to implement the economic studies in their daily decision-making practice. The negative attitude so far, could also be associated with the lack of incentives for them to employ rational decision making using cost-effectiveness approaches. It is human nature that they would assess between ‘risks and benefits’ to their own personal conveniences. It had been proposed, therefore, that shifting the compensation strategy for physician from ‘fee-for-service’ to ‘fee-for-performance’ as one of the steps to overcome the barriers (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Roseboom et al., 2017). However, Eddama and Coast (2008) argued if ‘fee-for-performance’ indeed a solution, judging from the experiences that the implementation of such system in US and in some extent in the UK, did not produce significant impact on the use of health economic evaluations by local decision makers. Perhaps, if this strategy will be implemented, the first thing to do is to define

the meaning of performance, followed by defining the techniques to measure it. Such thing, of course, required further study.

INTRINSIC BARRIERS

Several methodological issues had been addressed by the decision makers, although Erntoft (2011) found that methodological barriers perhaps only minor. Nonetheless, ‘introspective account’ is crucial if the economists desired to extend the implementation of economic studies in decision-making (Buxton, 2006).

ISSUES ON EQUITY AND ETHICAL CONCERNS

Many concern that health economic evaluation forsaken the equity consideration. For instance, some participants argued that equity and efficiency offered by economic studies did not blend well (Eddama and Coast, 2009). While some criticized QALYs for the inability to comprehend the actual patient’s experience and thus might not properly addressed the equity notion (Buxton, 2006), as in the context of valuing the detrimental hand injury between ordinary people and a pianist/musician (Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). However, despite the critic on equity continue to rise, there is no doubt that the mistrust mostly coming from the misunderstanding toward health economic evaluation as stated by Zwart-van Rijkom et al. (2000, pp. 158) that “*misunderstanding is an important factor in this criticism*”. Nonetheless, beside the continuous efforts from economists to rectify the equity concerns in health economics studies, a sound training of health economic evaluations for decision makers might worth to look at. Furthermore, some decision makers argued that health economic has failed to occupy the individual perspective because its nature to elaborate the societal benefits. This has been perceived by most of physicians as unethical, thus became the justification to reject health economics consideration in their priority-setting agenda. However, Roseboom et al. (2017) argued, that despite its subtlety, at the end, every physician ought to consider the health

outcomes for the whole population anyway. And since health and health care are complex in nature, therefore restricting the priority-setting based on individual needs alone may not be justice, even further in the long run could jeopardize the equality and equity of health care provisions. Further, even with the current effort to incorporate equity values to health economic analysis, it is still argued if such manoeuvre would bring significant impact in the acceptance of economic evaluation in decision making (Zwart-van Rijko, et al., 2000).

QUALITY AND VALIDITY CONCERNS

The concern in quality and validity could be seen as a ‘wake-up call’ to push the study of health economic evaluations to be more rigorous, reliable and relevant (Buxton, 2006). The modelling approach in economic studies, for example, has been doubted to be oversimplifying real life settings and ingrained with too many assumptions (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011; Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Roseboom et al., 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). However, such argumentation failed to grasp the main idea of health economic evaluation that it is existed to provide a rational priority-settings, while also capturing the actual problematic that a society faced in term of balancing the demands and needs. Nevertheless, providing the decision makers with high quality studies with reliable results which also in concordance with the decision makers contexts, are pivotal. Therefore, an establishment of solid database sources, such as NHS EED, which summarized the current assessments of cost-effectiveness in health care with an open access nature, might help to disseminate the studies for decision makers consideration further, while at the same time providing the space for easy appraisal by other authors (Hoffmann et al., 2002; Roseboom et al., 2017). As generally the reliability and availability intertwined and the participants complained that the appropriate study related to their issues often unavailable (Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000).

TRANSFERABILITY AND GENERALIZABILITY

In discussing the transferability of the economics study, local needs should be taken into account. Many had argued that economic studies were made in the ‘ivory tower’, therefore useless in term of the implementation for the local settings. Some decision makers, for example, criticized how most of the health economic studies were concentrated in assessing specific diseases or treatments which did not reflect the complexity of real life situation, with often larger issues to consider, as what most decision makers had to deal with (Hoffmann et al., 2002; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Likewise, other participants in different study argued that since the assessment often restricted to a particular group within population, the study results then perceived out of local contexts thus impractical (Eddama and Coast, 2009; Roseboom et al., 2017). Further, Roseboom et al. (2017) suggested that combining local issues and general population perspective in term of achieving the desired health outcomes might be one the possible solution to make the health economic studies more factual and feasible. Moreover, the role of modelling in health economic evaluation which occupied ‘too many assumptions’ had also cast doubt among decision makers to the fact that such approach may not reliable to represent the reality thus meaningless for daily decision-making practice (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011; Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Roseboom et al., 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). However, despite there is some truth in such views (Brousselle and Lessard, 2011), modelling in health economic evaluation is inevitable considering that costs and effects are complex and immense, thus mathematical calculation and abstract thinking needed to estimate the appropriate values (Brazier et al., 2007; Briggs et al., 2006; Kuntz and Weinstein, 2001; Mitton and Donaldson, 2004; Morris et al., 2007). After all, the decision makers indeed aware of these circumstances when they expressed that cost “*may vary extensively in reality due to factors such as jurisdiction...*” (Roseboom et al, 2017, pp. 5), and hence the probable explanation for such critics could be traced back to the lack of knowledge in the nature of health economics studies. Nonetheless, if the health economist wanted to boost the impact of its

studies to the local settings, understanding the nature of local contexts and conducting a research that more relevant to the local decision makers' problems are the appropriate strategy (Eddama and Coast, 2009).

The issue regarding how cost is varied among jurisdictions thus a health economics study conducted in different settings may not be applicable to others, has also raised decision makers' concerns (Roseboom et al., 2017; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Nevertheless, the lack of generalizability of economics studies became one of the barrier that impede the use of its results for decision-making process. Some respondents in UK local decision makers, for instance, had reported that 65% of the available health economic evaluations listed in NHS EED, were coming from United States. They argued therefore, whether it would be appropriate to adopt it to UK local framework (Hoffmann et al., 2002). Consequently, decision makers requested more studies addressing the international comparability of health economics analysis (Hoffmann and von der Schulenburg, 2000; Zwart-van Rijkom et al., 2000). Other suggested to provide universal model that could be easily replicated across geography or local boundaries (van Gool et al., 2007). Although, as the author continued that the data substitution in such case would face difficulty considering that some potential characteristics such as variation in financial structure, workforces availability, government incentives policy and difference in nature of the health care practices could not be readily addressed. Nevertheless, as the data variations between countries and settings existed, and "*there is no a priori reason why one should expect a given analytical approach to be equally appropriate in all situations*" Drummond et al. (1993, pp. 27), the authors then recommended the need for standardization. There are three key-points to consider in regards of the standardization establishment for economic studies: "1. *To distinguish between technical judgements and value judgments in study methodology; 2. To recognize that the importance of particular analytic viewpoints is likely to vary from setting to setting; and 3. To recognize that even perfect standardization will not necessarily permit simple*

comparisons or complete generalizability across cultural settings” (Drummond et al., 1993, pp. 31).

TIMELINESS

Correspondingly, there is issue about the timeliness of health economic studies. Some decision makers argued that since the local decision-making process is short-term in nature, the economic studies assessing the matters either not yet available or already outdated (Eddama and Coast, 2008; Roseboom et al., 2017). To answer this issue, UK with its NICE had produced a program called Single Technology Appraisals (STAs) intended to disseminate the results in targeted and in timely manner (Buxton, 2006). Although, what decision makers should aware, such approach would be prone to assumptions, as what decision makers wished to avoid.

CHAPTER VI CONCLUSION

Plenty have been discussed regarding the use of health economic evaluations in the actual decision-making process among local decision makers. Despite the studies coming from diverse geographical features, the findings almost identical, especially concerning the attitudes of micro-level decision makers toward health economics studies. Almost all the authors reported the evidences of the limited use of health economic evaluation for local priority-setting decision. Subsequently, several barriers already identified and some of the solutions to overcome it has already been proposed. However, judging that decision-making process is, in itself complex, further understanding needed to capture the real-life settings that these decision makers have to face in their daily practice. As Buxton (2006) argued that health economists should stand in the neutral position and adjusting their future recommendations more into accommodating the decision makers dilemma and problematical condition. Lessard et al. (2010) further suggesting that to understand the physician's contexts during their decision-making process, Bourdieu's theoretical approach can be used. To their explanation, Bourdieu's theory could explain how physician practice and decision making are the products of their individual subjectivity and societal influences. In different article, Lessard et al. (2009, pp. 3) said that *"economists leave out a very important part of social reality. Because of their socially constructed nature, understanding preferences, behaviours and markets required serious attention to social reality"*. Furthermore, both in meso-level and micro-level, all cried out for strong supports from the government and public. In the reality, financial and skills supports are desperately required to increase the uptake of health economic evaluations in the local health care decision-making. Finally, no health economists wanted their works merely useless at the end if the implementation continued limited as to quote satiric remark from Drummond (2004, pp. 9) in his concluding thought *"economic*

evaluation is sometimes used, is often not used, probably should more often be used, and ways can be found to increase its use. However, I might just be kidding myself!”

CHAPTER VII

RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE WORK

This systematic review has presented the convincing evidences how the actual use of economic evaluation in local health care decision-making somewhat limited. However, there is the need to further understand the barriers that impede the local decision makers in utilizing the result of the economic studies in their priority-settings agenda. As several respondents in several studies recognized the importance to rationale the scarce resources allocation in health care, it is paradoxical to see why to the current extend, some of them seemed to be reluctant in embedding the cost-effectiveness consideration in their decision-making process. Consequently, a qualitative approach with an appropriate study design like in-depth interviews or the combination of observation and interviews probably most suitable to address this objective. Furthermore, it also might worth to consider different approach using psychological or societal framework to understand the complexity of decision-making process, as suggested by Lessard et al. (2010) with their Bourdieu's theory. Accordingly, a study regarding the contexts of decision making process specifically designed for physicians (micro-level decision makers), since they were the one who acted as the front-liner with their direct contact with people, also crucial to be conducted in the future. Likewise, further research also required to assess what type of health economic evaluation that most appropriate for local decision makers with their unique attributes, as in the study about cost-consequences analysis or PBMA (Programme Budgeting Marginal Analysis) and their impact in local health priority-settings. Nevertheless, any future studies should also carefully consider the quality and the validity of their findings while also take a considerable amount of efforts to avoid the study biases.

REFERENCES

- Appleby, J., 2007. Data briefing. The NICE threshold. *The Health service journal*, 117(6074), pp.21.
- Aveyard, H., Payne, S. and Peston, N., 2016. *A Post-graduate's Guide to Doing a Literature Review in Health and Social Care*. England: Open University Press.
- Aveyard, H., 2014. *Doing a Literature Review in Health and Social Care*. 3rd ed. England: Open University Press.
- Barrett, B., 2011. Evidence, Values, Guidelines and Rational Decision-making. *J Gen Intern Med*, 27(2), pp. 238-40. DOI: 10.1007/s11606-011-1903-6.
- Bobinac, A, Van Exel, N.J.A, Rutten, F.F.H and Brouwer, W.B.F., 2012. Inquiry into the relationship between equity weights and the value of the QALY. *Value in health : the journal of the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research*, 15(8), pp.119-26. DOI: 10.1016/j.jval.2012.07.002.
- Brazier, J., Ratcliffe, J., Salomon, J.A. and Tsuchiya, A., 2007. *Measuring and Valuing Health Benefits for Economic Evaluation*. Reprint, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.
- Briggs, A., Sculpher, M. and Claxton, K., 2006. *Decision Modelling for Health Economic Evaluation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- British Medical Journal Publishing Group., 2002. Multicentre aneurysm screening study (MASS): cost effectiveness analysis of screening for abdominal aortic aneurysms based on four year results from randomised controlled trial. *BMJ*, 325(7373), p.1135. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.325.7373.1135.
- Brown, K. and Burrows, C., 1990. The sixth stool guaiac test: \$47 million that never was. *J Health Econ*, 9(4), pp.429-45.
- Brousselle, A. and Lessard, C., 2011. Economic evaluation to inform health care decision-making: Promise, pitfalls and a proposal for an alternative path. *Social Science & Medicine*, 72(6), pp. 832-839. DOI: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.01.008.
- Brouwer, W.B.F., Culyer, A.J., Van Exel, N.J.A. and Rutten, F.F.H., 2008. Welfarism vs. extra-welfarism. *Journal of health economics*, 27(2), pp. 325-338.
- Buchanan, J. and Wordsworth, S., 2015. Welfarism Versus Extra-Welfarism: Can the Choice of Economic Evaluation Approach Impact on the Adoption Decisions Recommended by Economic Evaluation Studies? *PharmacoEconomics*, 33(6), pp.571-579. DOI: 10.1007/s40273-015-0261-3.
- Buxton, M., 2006. Economic Evaluation and Decision Making in the UK. *PharmacoEconomics*, 24(11), pp.1133-1142. DOI: 10.2165/00019053-200624110-00009.
- CESifo DICE Report, 2008. *Bismarck Versus Beveridge: A Comparison of Social Insurance Systems in Europe*. [pdf] CESifo Group Munich. Available at: < <http://www.cesifo-group.de/ifoHome/facts/DICE/Social-Policy/Pensions/General-Structure/bismarck-beveridge-dicereport408-db6/fileBinary/bsimarck-beveridge-dicereport408-db6.pdf>> [Accessed 18 September 2017].

- Claxton, K., Martin, S., Soares, M., Rice, N., Spackman, E., Hinde, S., Devlin, N., Smith, P.C. and Sculpher, M., 2015. Methods for the estimation of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence cost-effectiveness threshold. *Health Technol Assess*, 19(14), pp. 1-503, v-vi. DOI: 10.3310/hta19140.
- Coast, J., 2009. Maximisation in extra-welfarism: A critique of the current position in health economics. *Social Science & Medicine*, 69(5), pp.786-92. DOI: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.06.026.
- Coast, J., Smith, R. and Lorgelly, P., 2008. Welfarism, extra-welfarism and capability: The spread of ideas in health economics. *Social Science & Medicine*, 67(7), p.1190-1198.
- Coyle, D. and Davies, L., 1993. How to assess cost-effectiveness: elements of a sound economic evaluation. In: Drummond, M. F., & Maynard, A., eds. 1993. *Purchasing and Providing Cost-Effective Health Care*. UK: Churchill Livingstone. Ch.5.
- Culyer, A.J., 1989. The normative economics of health care finance and provision. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 5(1), pp.34-58.
- de Koning, H. J., Martin van Ineveld, B., van Oortmarssen, G. J., de Haes, J. C. J. M., Collette, H. J. A., Hendriks, J. H. C. L. and van der Maas, P. J., 1991. Breast cancer screening and cost-effectiveness: Policy alternatives, quality of life considerations and the possible impact of uncertain factors. *Int. J. Cancer*, 49, pp. 531-537. DOI: 10.1002/ijc.2910490410.
- Dolan, P. and Edlin, R., 2002. Is it really possible to build a bridge between cost-benefit analysis and cost-effectiveness analysis? *Journal of Health Economics*, 21 (5), pp. 827-43.
- Donaldson, C., Currie, G. and Mitton, C., 2002. Cost effectiveness analysis in health care: contraindications. *BMJ*, 325(7369), pp. 891. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.325.7369.891.
- Douglas, H-R., Normand, C., 2005. Economic evaluation: what does a nurse manager need to know? *Journal of Nursing Management*, 13(5), pp.419-427. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2834.2005.00586.x.
- Drummond, M., Brandt, A., Luce, B. and Rovira, J., 1993. Standardizing methodologies for economic evaluation in health care: Practice, Problems, and Potential. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 9(1), pp. 26-36. DOI: 10.1017/S0266462300003007.
- Drummond, M.F., Sculpher, M.J., Torrance, G.W., O'Brien, B.J. and Stoddart, G.L., 2005. *Methods for the Economic Evaluation of Health Care Programmes*. 3rd ed. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Drummond, M., 2004. Economic Evaluation in Health Care: Is It Really Useful or Are We Just Kidding Ourselves? *Australian Economic Review*, 37(1), pp. 3-11. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-8462.2004.00304.x.
- Drummond, M.F., 1993a. The contribution of health economics to cost-effective health-care delivery. In: Drummond, M. F., & Maynard, A., eds. 1993. *Purchasing and Providing Cost-Effective Health Care*. UK: Churchill Livingstone. Ch.2.
- Drummond, M.F., 1993b. Health technology policy and health services research. In: Drummond, M. F., & Maynard, A., eds. 1993. *Purchasing and Providing Cost-Effective Health Care*. UK: Churchill Livingstone. Ch.15.
- Drummond, M., Brandt, A., Luce, B. and Rovira, J., 1993. Standardizing Methodologies for Economic Evaluation in Health Care: Practice, Problems, and Potential. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 9(1), pp.26-36. DOI: 10.1017/S0266462300003007.

- Eddama, O. and Coast, J., 2009. Use of economic evaluation in local health care decision-making in England: A qualitative investigation. *Health policy*, 89(3), pp. 261-270. DOI: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2008.06.004.
- Eddama, O. and Coast, J., 2008. A systematic review of the use of economic evaluation in local decision-making. *Health Policy*, 86(2-3), pp. 129-41. DOI: 10.1016/j.healthpol.2007.11.010.
- Ericsson, K., Bantje, T.A., Huber, R.M., Borg, S. and Bateman, E.D., 2006. Cost-effectiveness analysis of budesonide/formoterol compared with fluticasone in moderate-persistent asthma. *Respir Med.*, 100(4), pp.586-94. DOI: 10.1016/j.rmed.2005.09.032.
- Erntoft, S., 2011. Pharmaceutical Priority Setting and the Use of Health Economic Evaluations: A Systematic Literature Review. *Value in Health*, 14(4), pp.587-599. DOI: 10.1016/j.jval.2010.10.036.
- European Commission, 2004. *Aid Delivery Methods. Volume 1: Project Cycle Management Guidelines*. [pdf] Brussels: European Commission, Europaid Corporation Office. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/aid-delivery-methods-project-cycle-management-guidelines-vol-1_en> [Accessed 3 September 2017].
- Evans, D.B. and Hurley, S.F., 1995. The Application of Economic Evaluation Techniques in The Health Sector: The State of The Art. *Journal of International Development*, 7(3), pp. 503-524.
- Folland, S., Goodman, A.C. and Stano, M., 2004. *The Economic of Health and Health Care*. 4th ed. USA: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Franken, M., Heintz, E., Gerber-Grote, A. and Raftery, J., 2016. Health Economics as Rhetoric: The Limited Impact of Health Economics on Funding Decisions in Four European Countries. *Value in Health*, 19(8), pp.951-956. DOI: 10.1016/j.jval.2016.08.001.
- Frazier, A.L., Colditz, G.A., Fuchs, C.S. and Kuntz, K.M., 2000. Cost-effectiveness of Screening for Colorectal Cancer in the General Population. *JAMA*, 284(15), pp. 1954-1961. DOI: 10.1001/jama.284.15.1954.
- Frontline, 2015. *Health Care System – the Four Basic Models*. [online] Available at: <<http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/pages/frontline/sickaroundtheworld/countries/models.html>> [Accessed 18 September 2017].
- Furstenberg, F., 2016. Reconsidering Teenage Pregnancy and Parenthood. *Societies*, 6(4), pp. 33. DOI: 10.3390/soc6040033.
- Goeree, R. and Diaby, V., 2013. Introduction to health economics and decision-making: Is economics relevant for the frontline clinician? *Best Practice & Research Clinical Gastroenterology*, 27(6), pp.831-844. Doi: 10.1016/j.bpg.2013.08.016.
- Gomersall, J.S., Jadotte, Y.T., Xue, Y., Lockwood, S., Riddle, D. and Preda, A., 2015. Conducting systematic reviews of economic evaluations. *International Journal of Evidence-Based Healthcare*, 13(3), pp. 170-178. DOI: 10.1097/XEB.000000000000063.
- Gough, A., Oliver, S. and Thomas, J., eds., 2017. *An introduction to systematic reviews*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE.
- Gough, D., Thomas, J. and Oliver, S., 2012. Clarifying differences between review designs and methods. *Systematic Reviews*, 1(1), p.28. DOI: 10.1186/2046-4053-1-28.

Gravel, N. and Moyes, P., 2011. Utilitarianism or Welfarism: Does it Make a Difference? *halshs-00634010*.

Graves, N., McKinnon, L., Leggett, B. and Newman, B., 2005. Re-interpreting the data on the cost and effectiveness of population screening for colorectal cancer in Australia. *Australia and New Zealand Health Policy*, 2:10. Doi: 10.1186/1743-8462-2-10.

Gray, A. and Vale, L., 2003. Economic Evaluation for Decision-making. In: Scott, A., Maynard, A. and Elliott, R., eds., 2003. *Advances in Health Economics*. West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Ch.4.

Griebsch, I., Brown, J., Boggis, C., Dixon, A., Dixon, M., Easton, D., Eeles, R., Evans, D.G., Gilbert, F.J., Hawnaur, J., Kessar, P., Lakhani, S.R., Moss, S.M., Nerurkar, A., Padhani, A.R., Pointon, L.J., Pottterton, J., Thompson, D., Turnbull, L.W., Walker, L.G., Warren, R. and Leach, M.O., 2006. Cost-effectiveness of screening with contrast enhanced magnetic resonance imaging vs X-ray mammography of women at a high familial risk of breast cancer. *British Journal of Cancer*, 95(7), p.801-810. DOI: 10.1038/sj.bjc.6603356.

Henderson, D.R., 2008. *Opportunity Cost*. [online] Econlib. Available at: <http://www.econlib.org/library/Enc/OpportunityCost.html> [Accessed 7 September 2017]

Hewitt M., 2007. *How to Search and Critically Evaluate Research Literature*. The NIHR RDS for the East Midlands / Yorkshire & the Humber.

Hewitt-Taylor, J., 2017. *The Essential Guide to Doing a Health and Social Care Literature Review*. Oxon: Routledge.

Hjelmgren, J., Berggren, F. and Andersson, F., 2001. Health economic guidelines – similarities, differences and some implications. *Value in Health*, 4(3), pp.225-250. Doi: 10.1046/j.1524-4733.2001.43040.x.

Hoffman C. and von der Schulenburg, J.M.G., 2000. The influence of economic evaluation studies on decision making: A European survey. *Health Policy*, 52(3), pp. 179-92.

Hoffmann, C., Stoykova, B.A., Nixon, J., Glanville, J.M., Misso, K. and Drummond, M.F., 2002. Do health-care decision makers find economic evaluations useful? The findings of focus group research in UK health authorities. *Value Health*, 5(2), pp. 71-8. DOI: 10.1046/j.1524-4733.2002.52109.x.

Hutton, J., 2012. 'Health Economics' and the Evolution of Economic Evaluation of Health Technologies. *Health Economics*, 21(1), pp. 13-18. DOI: 10.1002/hec.1818.

Jefferson, T., Demicheli, V. and Vale, L., 2002. Quality of Systematic Reviews of Economic Evaluations in Health Care. *JAMA*, 287(21), pp. 2809-2812. Doi: 10.1001/jama.287.21.2809.

Kabisch, M., Ruckes, C., Seibert-Grafe, M. and Blettner, M., 2011. Randomized controlled trials: part 17 of a series on evaluation of scientific publications. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt international*, 108(39), pp.663-8. DOI: 10.3238/arztebl.2011.0663.

Katrak, P., Bialocerkowski, A.E., Massy-Westropp, N., Kumar, S., and Grimmer, K.A., 2004. A systematic review of the content of critical appraisal tools. *BMC medical research methodology*, 4, pp.22.

Kind, P. and Gudex, C., 1993. The role of QALYs in assessing priorities between health-care intervention. In: Drummond, M. F., & Maynard, A., eds. 1993. *Purchasing and Providing Cost-Effective Health Care*. UK: Churchill Livingstone. Ch.7.

- Kobelt, G., 2013. *Health Economics: An Introduction to Economic Evaluation*. 3rd ed. London: Office of Health Economics.
- Kuntz, K. and Weinstein, M., 2001. Modelling in economic evaluation. In: Drummond, M. and McGuire, A., eds., 2001. *Economic Evaluation in Health Care. Merging Theory with Practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Ch.7.
- Lessard, C., Contandriopoulos, AP. and Marie-Dominique, B., 2009. The role of economic evaluation in the decision-making process of family physicians: design and methods of a qualitative embedded multiple-case study. *BMC Family Practice*, 10(1), p.15. DOI: 10.1186/1471-2296-10-15.
- Lessard, C., Contandriopoulos, AP. and Marie-Dominique, B., 2010. The role (or not) of economic evaluation at the micro level: can Bourdieu's theory provide a way forward for clinical decision-making? *Soc Sci Med*, 70(12), pp. 1948-56. DOI: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2010.03.013.
- Maberley, D., Walker, H., Koushik, A. and Cruess, A., 2003. Screening for diabetic retinopathy in James Bay, Ontario: a cost-effectiveness analysis. *CMAJ*, 168(2), pp. 160-4.
- Marseille, E., Kahn, J., Mmiro, F. and Guay, L., 1999. Cost effectiveness of single-dose nevirapine regimen for mothers and babies to decrease vertical HIV-1 transmission in sub-Saharan Africa. *The Lancet*, 354(9181), pp.803-9.
- Mathes, T., Walgenbach, M., Antoine, S-L., Pieper, D. and Eikermann, M., 2014. Methods for Systematic Reviews of Health Economic Evaluations. *Medical Decision Making*, 34(7), pp. 826-840. DOI: 10.1177/0272989X14526470.
- Mathes, T., Jacobs, E., Morfeld, J-C. and Pieper, D., 2013. Methods of international health technology assessment agencies for economic evaluations- a comparative analysis. *BMC Health Serv Res*, 13, pp. 371. DOI: 10.1186/1472-6963-13-371.
- McCabe, C., Claxton, K., Culyer, A., 2008. The NICE Cost-Effectiveness Threshold What it is and What that Means. *PharmacoEconomics*, 26(9), pp.733-744. DOI: 10.2165/00019053-200826090-00004.
- McCaughey, D. and Bruning, N. S., 2010. Rationality versus reality: the challenges of evidence-based decision making for health policy makers. *Implementation Science*, 5, p.39-39. DOI: 10.1186/1748-5908-5-39.
- McGregor, M., 2003. Cost Utility analysis: Use QALYs only with great caution. *Canadian Medical Association Journal*, 168(4), pp. 433.
- McGuire, A., 2001. Theoretical concepts in the economic evaluation of health care. In: Drummond, M. and McGuire, A., eds., 2001. *Economic Evaluation in Health Care. Merging Theory with Practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Ch.1.
- McIntosh, E. and Luengo-Fernandez, R., 2006. Economic evaluation. Part 1: Introduction to the concepts of economic evaluation in health care. *Journal of Family Planning and Reproductive Health Care*, 32(2), p.107. DOI: 10.1783/147118906776276549.
- McPake, B., Kumaranayake, L. and Normand, C., 2002. *Health Economics. An International Perspective*. Reprint, New York: Routledge, 2003.
- Mitton, C. and Donaldson, C., 2004. *Priority Setting Toolkit. A guide to the use of economics in healthcare decision making*. London: BMJ books.

- Mooney, G.H. and Drummond, M.F., 1982. Part I (continued)- What is economics? *British Medical Journal*, 285 (6347), pp. 1024-1025.
- Mooney, G., 1989. QALYs: are they enough? A health economist's perspective. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 15(3), p.148. DOI: 10.1136/jme.15.3.148.
- Mooney, G., 1992. *Key Issues in Health Economics*. Hertfordshire: Harvester Wheatsheaf.
- Mooney, G. and Russell, E., 2003. Equity in Health Care: The Need for a New Economics Paradigm? In: Scott, A., Maynard, A. and Elliott, R., eds., 2003. *Advances in Health Economics*. West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Ch.11.
- Morris, S., Devlin, N. and Parkin, D., 2007. *Economic Analysis in Health Care*. Reprint, England: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2010.
- Munn, Z., Moola, S., Riitano, D. and Lisy, K., 2014. The Development of a Critical Appraisal Tool for Use in Systematic Reviews: Addressing Questions of Prevalence. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 3(3), pp.123-128. DOI: 10.15171/ijhpm.2014.71.
- NICE, 2012. *Methods for the development of NICE public health guidance (third edition)*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg4/chapter/incorporating-health-economics#economic-evidence-and-guidance-recommendations>> [Accessed 15 September 2017].
- Owens, D.K., 1998. Interpretation of Cost-Effectiveness Analyses. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 13(10), pp.716-717.
- Patel, R.S., Sharma, K.H., Kamath, N.A., Patel, N.H. and Thakkar, A.M., 2014. Cost-effectiveness analysis of nebivolol and metoprolol in essential hypertension: a pharmacoeconomic comparison of antihypertensive efficacy of beta blockers. *Indian J Pharmacol.*, 46(5), pp. 485-9. DOI: 10.4103/0253-7613.140577.
- Peeters, A., Schouten, J.S.A.G., Severens, J.L., Hendrikse, F., Prins, M.H., Webers, C.A.B., 2012. Latanoprost versus timolol as first choice therapy in patients with ocular hypertension A cost-effectiveness analysis. *Acta Ophthalmologica*, 90(2), pp.146-154. DOI: 10.1111/j.1755-3768.2009.01857.x.
- Pettitt, D.A., Raza, S., Naughton, B., Roscoe, A., Ramakrishnan, A., Ali, A., Davies, B., Dopson, S., Hollander, G., Smith, J. and Brindley, D.A., 2016. The Limitations of QALY: A Literature Review. *Journal of Stem Cell Research & Therapy*, 6(4), pp. 1-7. DOI: 10.4172/2157-7633.1000334.
- Pickhardt, P.J., Hassan, C., Laghi, A., Zullo, A., Kim, D.H. and Morini, S., 2007. Cost-effectiveness of colorectal cancer screening with computed tomography colonography. *Cancer*, 109, pp. 2213-2221. DOI: 10.1002/cncr.22668.
- Pignone, M., Saha, S., Hoerger, T. and Mandelblatt, J., 2002. Cost-Effectiveness Analyses of Colorectal Cancer Screening: A Systematic Review for the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. *Ann Intern Med*, 137, pp. 96-104. DOI: 10.7326/0003-4819-137-2-200207160-00007.
- Plans-Rubió, P., 2006. Cost-effectiveness analysis of cholesterol-lowering therapies in Spain. *Am J Cardiovasc Drugs*, 6(3), pp. 177-88.
- Prosser, L.A., Koplan, J.P., Neumann, P.J. and Weinstein, M.C., 2000. Barriers to using cost-effectiveness analysis in managed care decision making. *The American journal of managed care*, 6(2), pp.173-9.

- Raikou, M., Gray, A., Briggs, A., Stevens, R., Cull, C., McGuire, A., Fenn, P., Stratton, I., Holman, R. and Turner, R., 1998. Cost effectiveness analysis of improved blood pressure control in hypertensive patients with type 2 diabetes: UKPDS 40. *BMJ*, 317(7160), 720–726. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.317.7160.720.
- Raftery, J., 2014. NICE's Cost-Effectiveness Range: Should it be Lowered? *Pharmacoeconomics*, 32(7), pp.613-5.
- Rawles, J., 1989. Castigating QALYs. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 15(3), p.143. DOI: 10.1136/jme.15.3.143.
- Rawles, J. and Rawles, K., 1990. The QALY argument: a physician's and a philosopher's view. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 16(2), p.93. DOI: 10.1136/jme.16.2.93.
- Richardson, J. and Mckie, J., 2005. Empiricism, ethics and orthodox economic theory: What is the appropriate basis for decision-making in the health sector? *Social Science & Medicine*, 60(2), pp.265-275.
- Rice, T.H., 2003. *The economics of health reconsidered*. 2nd ed. Chicago: Health Administration Press.
- Roseboom, K.J., Van Dongen, J.M., Tompa, E., Van Tulder, M.W., Bosmans, J.E., 2017. Economic evaluations of health technologies in Dutch healthcare decision-making: a qualitative study of the current and potential use, barriers, and facilitators. *BMC health services research*, 17(1), pp.89. DOI: 10.1186/s12913-017-1986-9.
- Rutten, F., 1996. Economic evaluation and health care decision-making. *Health Policy*, 36(3), pp. 215-229. DOI: 10.1016/0168-8510(96)00814-7.
- Sarasin, F.P., Majno, P.E., Llovet, J.M., Bruix, J., Mentha, G. and Hadengue, A., 2001. Living donor liver transplantation for early hepatocellular carcinoma: A life-expectancy and cost-effectiveness perspective. *Hepatology*, 33(5), pp.1073-1079. DOI: 10.1053/jhep.2001.23311.
- Scott, R.D., Solomon, S.L. and McGowan, J.E., 2001. Applying Economic Principles to Health Care. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 7(2), pp. 282-285. DOI: 10.3201/eido702.700282.
- Sculpher, M.J., Claxton, K., Drummond, M. and McCabe, C., 2006. Whither trial-based economic evaluation for health care decision making? *Health Economics*, 15(7), pp. 677-687. DOI: 10.1002/hec.1093.
- Seixas, B.V., 2017. Welfarism and extra-welfarism: a critical overview. *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*, 33(8). DOI: 10.1590/0102-311X00014317.
- Sen, A., 1979. Personal Utilities and Public Judgements: Or What's Wrong with Welfare Economics. *The Economic Journal*, 89(355), pp.537-558. DOI: 10.2307/2231867.
- Sheldon, T.A., Song, F. and Smith, G.D., 1993. Critical appraisal of the medical literature: how to assess whether health-care interventions do more good than harm. In: Drummond, M. F., & Maynard, A., eds. 1993. *Purchasing and Providing Cost-Effective Health Care*. UK: Churchill Livingstone. Ch.3.
- Sheldon, T.A, Cullum, N., Dawson, D., Lankshear, A., Lowson, K., Watt, I., West, P., Wright, D. and Wright, J., 2004. What's the evidence that NICE guidance has been implemented? Results from a national evaluation using time series analysis, audit of patients' notes, and interviews. *BMJ*, 329(7473), pp.999. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.329.7473.999.
- Smith, K.J. And Roberts, M.S., 2000. The cost-effectiveness of sildenafil. *Ann Intern Med*, 132, pp. 933-937.

- Soares, M.O., 2012. Is the QALY blind, deaf and dumb to equity? NICE's considerations over equity. *British Medical Bulletin*, 101(1), pp. 17–31. DOI: 10.1093/bmb/ldso03.
- Tengs, T.O., Meyer, G., Siegel, J.E., Pliskin, J.S., Graham, J.D. and Weinstein, M.C., 1996. Oregon's Medicaid Ranking and Cost- Effectiveness. *Medical Decision Making*, 16(2), pp.99-107. DOI: 10.1177/0272989X9601600201.
- Ternopil State Medical University, no date. *Methods of pharmaceconomic evaluation: Cost of Illness, Cost-Minimization Analysis, Cost-Effectiveness Analysis*. [online] Available at: http://intranet.tdmu.edu.ua/data/kafedra/internal/upr_ekon/classes_stud/en/pharm/prov_pharm/ptn/Pharmacoeconomics/4/3%20Methods%20of%20pharmaceconomic%20evaluation.%20Cost%20of%20Illness.%20Cost-Minimization,%20Cost-Effectiveness.htm. <Accessed 27 September 2017>
- Towse, A., 2009. Should NICE's threshold range for cost per QALY be raised? Yes. *BMJ*, 338, b.181. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.b181.
- Towse, A. and Pritchard, C., 2002. National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE): Is Economic Appraisal Working? *Pharmacoeconomics*, 20(3), pp. 95-105.
- Tsuchiya, A. and Williams A., 2001. Welfare economics and economic evaluation. In: Drummond, M. and McGuire, A., eds., 2001. *Economic Evaluation in Health Care. Merging theory with practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Ch.2.
- van Gool, K., Gallego, G., Haas, M., Viney, R., Hall, J. and Ward, R., 2007. Economic Evidence at the Local Level. *Pharmacoeconomics*, 25(12), pp.1055-1062. DOI: 10.2165/00019053-200725120-00006.
- Wagstaff, A., 1991. QALYs and the equity-efficiency trade-off. *Journal of Health Economics*, 10(1), pp.21-41. DOI: 10.1016/0167-6296(91)90015-F.
- Walker, A., Whynes, D.K., Thomas, W.M., Chamberlain, J.O. and Hardcastle, J.D., 1991. Retesting positive results in screening for colorectal cancer: a marginal analysis. *Applied Economics*, 23, pp. 1015-1017.
- Wang, L.Y., Roman, B.R., Migliacci, J.C., Palmer, F.L., Tuttle, R.M., Shaha, A.R., Shah, J.P., Patel, S.G. and Ganly, I., 2015. Cost-effectiveness analysis of papillary thyroid cancer surveillance. *Cancer*, 121(23), pp. 4132-4140.
- Wagner, J.L., Herdman, R.C. and Wadhwa, S., 1991. Cost Effectiveness of Colorectal Cancer Screening in the Elderly. *Ann Intern Med*, 115, pp. 807–817. DOI: 10.7326/0003-4819-115-10-807.
- Whitehead, S.J. and Ali, S., 2010. Health outcomes in economic evaluation: the QALY and utilities. *British Medical Bulletin*, 96(1), pp.5-21. DOI: 10.1093/bmb/ldq033.
- Williams, I., Mciver, S., Moore, D. and Bryan, S., 2008. The use of economic evaluations in NHS decision-making: a review and empirical investigation. *Health technology assessment (Winchester, England)*, 12(7), pp.iii, ix-x, 1-175.
- Wu, O., Knill-Jones, R., Wilson, P. and Craig, N., 2004. The impact of economic information on medical decision making in primary care. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, 10(3), pp.407-411. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2753.2004.00490.x.

Zwart-van Rijkom, J., Leufkens, H., Busschbach, J., Broekmans, A. and Rutten, F., 2000. Differences in Attitudes, Knowledge and Use of Economic Evaluations in Decision-Making in The Netherlands. *Pharmacoeconomics*, 18(2), pp.149-160. DOI: 10.2165/00019053-200018020-00005.

APPENDIX I: CASP CHECKLIST QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

10 questions to help you make sense of qualitative research

How to use this appraisal tool

Three broad issues need to be considered when appraising a qualitative study:

- Are the results of the study valid? (Section A)
- What are the results? (Section B)
- Will the results help locally? (Section C)

The 10 questions on the following pages are designed to help you think about these issues systematically. The first two questions are screening questions and can be answered quickly. If the answer to both is “yes”, it is worth proceeding with the remaining questions.

There is some degree of overlap between the questions, you are asked to record a “yes”, “no” or “can’t tell” to most of the questions. A number of italicised prompts are given after each question. These are designed to remind you why the question is important. Record your reasons for your answers in the spaces provided.

These checklists were designed to be used as educational pedagogic tools, as part of a workshop setting, therefore we do not suggest a scoring system. The core CASP checklists (randomised controlled trial & systematic review) were based on JAMA 'Users' guides to the medical literature 1994 (adapted from Guyatt GH, Sackett DL, and Cook DJ), and piloted with health care practitioners.

For each new checklist a group of experts were assembled to develop and pilot the checklist and the workshop format with which it would be used. Over the years overall adjustments have been made to the format, but a recent survey of checklist users reiterated that the basic format continues to be useful and appropriate.

Referencing: we recommend using the Harvard style citation, i.e.:

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2017). CASP (insert name of checklist i.e. Qualitative Research) Checklist. [online] Available at: URL. Accessed: Date Accessed.

©CASP this work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution – Non Commercial-Share A like. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/> www.casp-uk.net

Screening Questions

1. Was there a clear statement of the aims Yes Can't tell No **of the research?**

HINT: Consider

- What was the goal of the research?
- Why it was thought important?
- Its relevance

2. Is a qualitative methodology appropriate? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- If the research seeks to interpret or illuminate the actions and/or subjective experiences of research participants
- Is qualitative research the right methodology for addressing the research goal?

Is it worth continuing?

Detailed questions

3. Was the research design appropriate to Yes Can't tell No **address the aims of the research?**

HINT: Consider

- If the researcher has justified the research design (E.g. have they discussed how they decided which method to use)?

4. Was the recruitment strategy appropriate to the Yes Can't tell No **aims of the research?**

HINT: Consider

- If the researcher has explained how the participants were selected
- If they explained why the participants they selected were the most appropriate to provide

access to the type of knowledge sought by the study

- If there are any discussions around recruitment (e.g. why some people chose not to take part)

5. Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- If the setting for data collection was justified
- If it is clear how data were collected (e.g. focus group, semi-structured interview etc.)
- If the researcher has justified the methods chosen
- If the researcher has made the methods explicit (e.g. for interview method, is there an indication of how interviews were conducted, or did they use a topic guide)?
- If methods were modified during the study. If so, has the researcher explained how and why?
- If the form of data is clear (e.g. tape recordings, video material, notes etc)
- If the researcher has discussed saturation of data

6. Has the relationship between researcher and participants been adequately considered? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- If the researcher critically examined their own role, potential bias and influence during
 - (a) Formulation of the research questions
 - (b) Data collection, including sample recruitment and choice of location
- How the researcher responded to events during the study and whether they considered the implications of any changes in the research design

7. Have ethical issues been taken into consideration? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- If there are sufficient details of how the research was explained to participants for the

reader to assess whether ethical standards were maintained

- If the researcher has discussed issues raised by the study (e.g. issues around informed consent or confidentiality or how they have handled the effects of the study on the participants during and after the study)
 - If approval has been sought from the ethics committee
-

8. Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- If there is an in-depth description of the analysis process
- If thematic analysis is used. If so, is it clear how the categories/themes were derived from the data?
- Whether the researcher explains how the data presented were selected from the original sample to demonstrate the analysis process
- If sufficient data are presented to support the findings
- To what extent contradictory data are taken into account
- Whether the researcher critically examined their own role, potential bias and influence during analysis and selection of data for presentation

9. Is there a clear statement of findings? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- If the findings are explicit
 - If there is adequate discussion of the evidence both for and against the researchers arguments
 - If the researcher has discussed the credibility of their findings (e.g. triangulation, respondent validation, more than one analyst)
 - If the findings are discussed in relation to the original research question
-

10. How valuable is the research?

HINT: Consider

- If the researcher discusses the contribution the study makes to existing knowledge or understanding e.g. do they consider the

findings in relation to current practice or policy?, or relevant research-based literature?

- If they identify new areas where research is necessary
- If the researchers have discussed whether or how the findings can be transferred to other populations or considered other ways the research may be used

APPENDIX II: CASP CHECKLIST QUALITATIVE SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

10 questions to help you make sense of a Systematic Review

How to use this appraisal tool

Three broad issues need to be considered when appraising a systematic review study:

Are the results of the study valid? (Section A)

What are the results? (Section B)

Will the results help locally? (Section C)

The 10 questions on the following pages are designed to help you think about these issues systematically. The first two questions are screening questions and can be answered quickly. If the answer to both is “yes”, it is worth proceeding with the remaining questions.

There is some degree of overlap between the questions, you are asked to record a “yes”, “no” or “can’t tell” to most of the questions. A number of italicised prompts are given after each question. These are designed to remind you why the question is important. Record your reasons for your answers in the spaces provided.

These checklists were designed to be used as educational pedagogic tools, as part of a workshop setting, therefore we do not suggest a scoring system. The core CASP checklists (randomised controlled trial & systematic review) were based on JAMA 'Users' guides to the medical literature 1994 (adapted from Guyatt GH, Sackett DL, and Cook DJ), and piloted with health care practitioners.

For each new checklist a group of experts were assembled to develop and pilot the checklist and the workshop format with which it would be used. Over the years overall adjustments have been made to the format, but a recent survey of checklist users reiterated that the basic format continues to be useful and appropriate.

Referencing: we recommend using the Harvard style citation, i.e.:

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2017). CASP (insert name of checklist i.e. Systematic Review) Checklist. [online] Available at: *URL*. Accessed: *Date Accessed*.

©CASP this work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution – Non Commercial-Share A like. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/> www.casp-uk.net

(A) Are the results of the review valid?

Screening Questions

1. Did the review address a clearly focused question? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: An issue can be 'focused' in terms of

- The population studied
- The intervention given
- The outcome considered

2. Did the authors look for the right type of papers? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: 'The best sort of studies' would

- Address the review's question
- Have an appropriate study design (usually RCTs for papers evaluating interventions)

Is It worth continuing?

Detailed Questions

3. Do you think all the important, relevant studies were included? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Look for

- Which bibliographic databases were used
- Follow up from reference lists
- Personal contact with experts
- Search for unpublished as well as published studies
- Search for non-English language studies

4. Did the review's authors do enough to assess the quality of the included studies? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: The authors need to consider the rigour of the studies they have identified. Lack of rigour may affect the studies' results. ("All that glitters is not gold" Merchant of Venice – Act II Scene 7)

5. If the results of the review have been combined, was it reasonable to do so?

Yes

Can't tell

No

HINT: Consider whether

- The results were similar from study to study
- The results of all the included studies are clearly displayed
- The results of the different studies are similar
- The reasons for any variations in results are discussed

(B) What are the results?

6. What are the overall results of the review?

HINT: Consider

- If you are clear about the review's 'bottom line' results
- What these are (numerically if appropriate)
- How were the results expressed (NNT, odds ratio etc)

7. How precise are the results?

HINT: Look at the confidence intervals, if given

(C) Will the results help locally?

Yes

Can't tell

No

8. Can the results be applied to the local population?

HINT: Consider whether

- The patients covered by the review could be sufficiently different to your population to cause concern
- Your local setting is likely to differ much from that of the review

9. Were all important outcomes considered? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider whether

- Is there other information you would like to have seen

10. Are the benefits worth the harms and costs? Yes Can't tell No

HINT: Consider

- Even if this is not addressed by the review, what do you think?